

Project Number: (101018756)

Project Acronym: (GTCLC-NEG)

Project title: (Development of an innovative Gas Turbine Chemical Looping Combustor for Carbon
Negative Power Generation)

Periodic Technical Report Part B

Period covered by the report: from 01/07/2021 to 30/06/2023

Periodic report – FINAL

1. Explanation of the work carried out by the beneficiaries and overview of the progress

1.1 Objectives

The project has fully achieved its objectives and milestones for the period. The project objectives have been reported at page 2 of part B-1 and are also listed in table 1. It is reported also in part B-1 that there is a biunivocal correspondence between project Milestones and project Objectives.

Table 1: Project Scientific objectives and Milestones

Project Scientific objectives	Work carried out during the fellowship
1) produce 4 innovative bimetallic oxygen carriers (O1) and characterize their performance	<p>In the Workpackage 1 the Marie Curie fellow has produced 6 oxygen carriers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fe₂₀γAl - Ni₁₈αAl - Ilmenite - Tierga ore - Iron-Manganese-Titanium based oxygen carriers - Manganese-Iron Oxygen carriers <p>The production techniques and methods are reported in the deliverable D1.1. Their performances were characterized with the following analytical techniques: ICP-OES, TGA, crushing strength analyser, particle size distribution analyser, skeletal density analyser, porosimeter, BET analysis, XRD, SEM. The results of the characterization of the oxygen carriers are described in D1.2. Results on characterization of ilmenite particles as an oxygen carrier were included in an article published in FUEL journal, see [1]. In addition, characterization of Nickel- and Iron-based materials were useful for the achievement of the subsequent objectives, being relevant for the publication of the following articles: [2], [3], [4], [5] and [6].</p>
2) perform tests of chemical-looping combustion of 3 biofuels (pyrolysis oils, syngas and biogas) (O2) in high pressure (1-1.5 MPa) and high temperature (1200-1300°C) batch fluidized reactors (to assess attrition effects)	<p>Two experimental campaigns have been performed testing two different oxygen carriers in a batch fluidized bed reactor. Respectively Fe₂₀γAl and Ni₁₈αAl have been tested with biomethane at the following temperatures: 950°C, 1000°C, 1050°C, 1100°C, 1150°C, 1200°C. Higher temperatures could not be achieved in the reactor due to oxygen carrier sintering. Main results of these tests are reported in the deliverable D2. Complete characterization of the oxygen carrier has been performed once again after the tests, using the following analytical techniques: ICP-OES, TGA, crushing strength analyser, particle size distribution analyser, skeletal density analyser, porosimeter, BET analysis, XRD, SEM. Also these results are proposed in deliverable D2.</p> <p>Then, other experimental results on hydrogen and carbon monoxide have been used to model syngas behavior with different oxygen carriers. The results of the model which is set to work on pressurized conditions have been published in FUEL journal, see [2]. Those results have been presented during the MIT Applied Energy Symposium (MITAB 2022) in a keynote speech and are available in the you tube channel of the GTCLC-</p>

	<p>NEG Marie Curie Project¹. Another model of the reactor with iron oxygen carrier was realized based on experimental data using MFIX software, developed by the National Energy Technology Laboratory of the USDOE, Morgantown, US; see [3]. Results were presented at the NETL 2022 Workshop on Multiphase Flow Science, see ²</p> <p>Finally, continuous tests were performed from April 2022 to March 2023 using a continuous Chemical Looping combustor designed for liquid fuels. In this plant, bio-oil and glycerol were combusted. The results of these tests are reported in the Deliverable D4.</p> <p>This work allowed to analyze the performance of three biofuels (biomethane, bio-oil and glycerine) for the development of Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage Technologies, based on chemical looping combustion.</p>
<p>3) develop 1 particle model: where main kinetics aspect of redox reactions are analyzed in critical conditions; 1 0D model of the CLC reactor; 1 scaled up model in Aspen of the GTCLC plant (O3)</p>	<p>A particle model has been developed for the Ni18αAl oxygen carrier. Reaction kinetics with the main reducing gases present in CLC were determined as a function of the temperature, gas concentration and total pressure. Main results are described in Deliverable D3.1.</p> <p>A 0D model for the fuel reactor was adapted to consider the pressurized operation of a CLC unit. Deliverable “D3.2 0D reactor model” reports the most important results of the model, which were published in FUEL journal [4].</p> <p>In addition, advanced Computing Fluid Dynamic (CFD) models were developed to delve into relevant aspects for the reactor design, such as fluid dynamics and heat transfer. Main results were published in [2] and [3].</p> <p>Aspen Plus models were developed to integrate the CLC reactors with a Gas Turbine (GTCLC). In addition, the main effects of the design of the CLC unit on the GT performance were evaluated. Results were published in three journal papers [4],[5, 6] and also presented at:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the conference of the Italian Thermotechnical Association (ATI) 2022 [7] - the 14th International Conference on Applied Energy - ICAE2022 (2022); see ³; - the 6th International Conference on Chemical Looping 2022, which was held from 19th September to 22nd September in the city of Zaragoza Spain and it was organized by ICB-CSIC, the hosting Institution of the Marie Curie Project. For the presentation see⁴ -and at the American Society of Mechanical Engineers Turbo Expo Conference of Boston on June 2023, see⁵.

¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CCPcYeL3NSc&t=35s>

² <https://zenodo.org/record/7213734>

³ <https://zenodo.org/record/7213742>

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/record/7213715>

⁵ <https://zenodo.org/record/8002251>

<p>4) test the best performing oxygen carrier in a recirculated multifuel 1 kW fluidized bed reactor, optimizing the reactor injection and hot exhausts cleaning, (O4) to obtaining carbon conversion > 80%; CO₂ output > 90%;</p>	<p>As already said, continuous tests were performed from April 2022 to March 2023 using a continuous Chemical Looping combustor designed for liquids. In this plant, biooil and glycerol were combusted. This allowed to analyze the performance of biofuels for the development of Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage Technologies, based on chemical looping combustion. The results of these tests are reported in the Deliverable D4. Carbon conversion and CO₂ output have been according to the previously fixed targets.</p>
<p>5) prepare 1 manual of guidelines and exploitation plan for the design of CLC combustors to be used with GTs; conduct 1 system study in collaboration with BHGE, on the integration of the proposed CLC reactor into a power generation unit, (O5) with cost of electricity < 100 €/MWh, GTCLC electrical efficiency > 50%. This will end up with GTCLC design guidelines.</p>	<p>A set of guidelines has been prepared in collaboration with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Instituto de Carboquímica, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (ICB-CSIC), hosting institution; Spain - Chalmers University, Sweden; - Zaragoza University, Spain - SINTEF Energy, Norway - State Key Laboratory on Coal Combustion in HUST, China - John A Paulson School of Engineering and Applied Sciences, Harvard University, US. - University of Perugia, Italy - Baker Hughes, Italy <p>The guidelines have been revised by Baker Hughes and University of Tampere and compiled in Deliverable 5.1. They have been published in a high impact factor journal like Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews (IF 15.9), see [8]. Economic and performance targets have been compared with commercial gas turbines and Allam Cycle using internal data of Baker Hughes company and have met the expectations.</p>

While the Milestones correspond basically with the Objective of the project, the list of deliverables produced for each workpackage is shown in table 2.

Table 2: List of Deliverables per Workpackage

Workpackage	Deliverables
WP1: OC preparation & characterization (July 2021 – January 2022)	D1.1: Oxygen carriers preparation D1.2: Oxygen carriers characterization
WP2: Batch Fluidized Bed (FB) reactors tests (February 2022 – December 2022)	D2: Batch tests
WP3: Modelling work (February 2022 – June 2023)	D3.1: Particle model D3.2: 0D reactor model D3.3: Aspen model
WP4: Continuous CLC Reactor tests (April 2022- March 2023)	D4: Continuous CLC tests
WP5: Plant design and optimization (April 2022- June 2022)	D5.1: Guidelines D5.2: Exploitation plan

All the deliverables can be accessed from the repository of the project, see⁶, and the website of the project, see⁷.

In table 3 we illustrate instead the Training objectives derived by page 4 of Part B-1.

Table 3: Project Training objectives

Project Training objectives	Work carried out during the fellowship
T1: participate to the financial management of the action	The researcher participated actively to the financial management of the action collaborating with Fajes Aznar, Concepción to check salary aspects and taxes. Gracia Ruiz, Ana Cristina for the payment of conferences and Soriano Roche, M ^a José for mobility allowance expenses. Besides this I collaborated with my supervisor Dr. Alberto Abad for lab and daily materials expenses. Further training has been done in Coursera with the courses of the iMBA degree on Financial and Project Management Aspect. A course on Project Management which is propaedeutically for the certification of the Project Management Institute has also been done during the Marie Curie Project.
T2: training on oxygen carrier preparation through impregnation, mechanical mixing (pelletisation) or granulation	As reported in the deliverable D1.1 I have been trained in the following oxygen carrier preparation techniques: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Impregnation - Mechanical mixing - Spray granulation <p>I had the chance to prepare 6 types of oxygen carriers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fe₂₀γAl - Ni₁₈αAl - Ilmenite - Tierga ore - Iron-Manganese-Titanium based oxygen carriers - Manganese-Iron Oxygen carriers
T3: training on oxygen carrier characterization through XRD, SEM and BET analysis	Characterization of the oxygen carrier was performed both: before and after the batch tests. The main analysis performed were: ICP-OES, TGA, crushing strength analyzer, particle size distribution analyzer, skeletal density analyzer, porosimeter, BET analysis, XRD, SEM. I participated both: to the analysis with the specific technicians of the analytical lab and also to data interpretation, guided by my research mates: Dr. Arturo Cabello and Dr. Margarita de Las Obras Loscertales.
T4: training on using batch Fluidized Bed reactors;	I have learned how to perform reactivity tests in fluidized beds. I have learned how determine suitable gas flow to properly operate a fluidized bed reactor, as well as mount and dismount the batch reactor, check pressure drop and gas leakages, set the gas analyzers, elaborate the data and check the energy and mass balances inside the reactor. The tests performed on the fluidized bed reactors have lasted more than 200 hours. This allowed me to achieve great experience on the management of these plants.
T5: Training on continuous fluidized bed reactor	I learned how to operate and control a PLC unit consisting on two interconnected fluidized bed reactors. Thus, it was required to regulate the

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/communities/gtclc-neg/?page=1&size=20>

⁷ <https://pietrobartocci.wixsite.com/gtclc-neg>

	oxygen carrier circulation rate and control the reacting temperature to optimize process parameters. I learned how to set up the data acquisition system, inject the liquid biofuels inside the plant, design liquid mass flow and gases mass flow to grant the required velocity of fluidization and oxygen carrier circulation inside the reactor. I also learned how to measure chemical looping combustion efficiency based on carbon dioxide yields and fuel conversion rate and also how to calculate main plant configuration characteristics, like circulation rate and oxygen carrier inventory.
T6: Training on modeling CLC in Aspen Plus	The training has been performed with hands on work made in collaboration with Dr. Arturo Cabello on both Aspen Plus and Aspen HYSIS. Besides this a training course of UDEMY of a total of 13 hours on Aspen Plus (“Aspen Plus Masterclass: From beginner to advanced user”).
T7&T8: Training on industrial fluidized bed reactors and gas turbines	During the secondment in Baker Hughes in Florence and the collaboration with Tampere University, the Individual Fellow had the opportunity to see industrial applications of large scale fluidized bed plants and also the implementation of carbon capture and storage in gas turbine innovative plants. Thanks to this experience it was possible to develop the guidelines for designing carbon capture and storage technologies based on biofuels combustion in gas turbines. Especially with Baker Hughes collaboration it was possible to compare the technical aspect of the GTCLC-NEG plant with an innovative plant based on the Allam Cycle, which is currently under development.
Complementary training	The list of all the complementary training is proposed in table 4.

Other complementary training courses are shown in table 4.

Table 4: List of training activities done during the Marie Curie Project

Training Activity	Date
CSIC Summer School on the Sustainable Energy Challenges - El reto de la energía hacia los objetivos de desarrollo sostenible-, Jaca, Spain	7-9 July, Jaca, Spain, 2021
NETL 2021 Workshop on Multiphase Flow Science	3-5 August, 2021
LARGE-SCALE ATOMIC/MOLECULAR MASSIVELY PARALLEL SIMULATOR USERS' WORKSHOP AND SYMPOSIUM	10—13, August, 2021
18th Multiphase Flow Conference & Short Course, Dresden 2021	8-12 November 2021, Dresden, Germany (online)
How to optimize Biomass Boilers performance efficiency with Digital Twin?	3 rd March 2022
Entrepreneurial Researchers and Innovation, organized by the Spanish MCAA	18 th May 2022
GENERAL INTRODUCTION TO PHYTON (Organised by the Spanish MCAA)	19-20 July 2022
ASME “Evolution of the internal combustion engine for ultra-high efficiency and near-zero emissions: RCCI and GCI	22 nd July, 2022
NETL 2022 Workshop on Multiphase Flow Science	2-3 August, 2022, online
Aspen Plus V11 Masterclass: From beginner to advanced user	14 th November 2022

CSIC, Técnicas Avanzadas de Machine Learning y su aplicación (con R) en Investigación Científica	13-24 th March, 2023
CSIC-ICB: Advanced Training on Gas Sorption with Dr. Martin Thomas	26 th April, 2023
TRAINING ON ENTERPREUNERSHIP AND BUSINESS	
ACCY 503 Managerial Accounting	9 th July 2021
BADM 572 Statistics Management Decision Making	28 th September 2021
BADM 520 Marketing Management	21 st September 2021
BADM 567 Process Management	22 nd November 2021
ACCY 500 Accounting Measurement, Reporting, and Control	3 rd March 2022
ECON 528 Microeconomics for Business	23 rd April 2022
FIN 571 Money and Banking	23 rd June 2022
MBA 552 Fostering Creative Thinking	21 st June 2022
MBA 561 Introduction to Business Analytics with R	12 th August 2022
MBA 562 Intro to Business Analytics: Communicating with Data	22 nd September 2022
BADM 508 Leadership & Teams	24 th August 2022
MBA 563 Data Toolkit: Business Data Modeling and Predictive Analytics	26 th October 2022
MBA 564 Applying Data Analytics in Marketing	16 th November 2022
MBA 564 Applying Data Analytics in Accounting	26 th November 2022
FIN 511 Investments Finance	12 th March 2023

1.2 Explanation of the work carried out per WP (Work Package)

- Main results per workpackage

Results and progress of the activities are described for each workpackage in detail. Then, details on the non-scientific management activities will be presented after the descriptions of the workpackages.

WP1: OC preparation & characterization (July 2021 – January 2022)

In the first workpackage the oxygen carriers were prepared with the following techniques:

- Impregnation
- Mechanical mixing
- Spray granulation

Here is proposed the description of the preparation process and also some of the samples obtained.

The **mechanical mixing method** is suitable for both ores and synthetic materials. Those materials can be mixed after decreasing their size to around 100–300 μm to make them suitable for fluidized bed operation.

Mechanical mixing yields fluidizable particles without a very costly procedure and is, therefore, commonly used. The equipment used for this sake at the Instituto de Carboquímica is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Hydraulic press for the production of pelletized oxygen carriers

The **spray granulation process** converts a water-containing solution, paste or suspension or a melt into a granule. The granulation and the drying processes take place at the same time. The granules can be calcinated once the preparation is finished. The facilities used for spray granulation at the Instituto de Carboquímica (CSIC) are shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Spray granulator in a spouted bed system (left) display (center) and final product (right) at the Laboratories of the Instituto de Carboquímica in Zaragoza, Spain

The process to produce **mixed iron and manganese** oxygen carriers is shown in figure 3.

Figure 3: Mixed iron-manganese Oxygen carriers preparation

In conventional impregnation technique, deposition of the species containing the element to be deposited takes place by precipitation during drying. The drying step is critical since the impregnation solution migrates and the metal is deposited mainly where the solvent evaporates. The main drawback of the impregnation method is the limited amount of active phase that can be introduced into the support in each stage. To optimize the impregnation and to reduce the number of preparation stages, the **hot impregnation method** with the solution and the support at higher temperatures can be used. The supported OC were prepared using Fe or Ni nitrate as metal precursor. For example, for the Ni-based oxygen carrier ($\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (>99.5% Panreac) was used. The materials for the support were commercial $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ (Puralox NWA-155, Sasol Germany GmbH) particles of +100–300 μm , with a density of 1.3 g/cm^3 and a porosity of 55.4%, and $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ particles of +100–300 μm , obtained by calcination of the $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ particles at 1150 $^\circ\text{C}$ during 2 h, with a density of 2 g/cm^3 and a porosity of 47.3%. The Ni-based OC were prepared by this method at ambient temperature as described in a previous work [9] using the $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ as supports. The OC were prepared by addition of a volume of a saturated solution (20 $^\circ\text{C}$, 4.2 M) of Ni nitrate corresponding to the total pore volume of the support particles. The aqueous solution was slowly added to the support particles, with thorough stirring at room temperature. The desired active phase loading was achieved by applying successive impregnations followed by calcination at 550 $^\circ\text{C}$, in air atmosphere for 30 min, to decompose the impregnated metal nitrates into insoluble metal oxide. Finally, the carriers were sintered for 1 h at 950 $^\circ\text{C}$. One OC impregnated on $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ with a NiO weight content of 21% and one OC impregnated on $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ with a NiO weight content of 11% were prepared. The complete process is shown in figure 4.

Figure 4: Oxygen carrier preparation with impregnation method and different supports

In Figure 4 we see the methods used to prepare Ni18 α Al and Ni18 γ Al.

To reduce the number of impregnation stages, the impregnation method at hot conditions was also used. A modification of the incipient wet impregnation method was carried out by using a hot nickel nitrate solution in order to increase the solubility of the nickel nitrate. Different OC were prepared by impregnation of $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ support heated at 80 $^\circ\text{C}$ in a planetary mixer using a saturated nickel nitrate solution at 60–80 $^\circ\text{C}$ (6 M). In this

condition the amount of nickel deposited, in one step, over the porous support was increased compared with the impregnation method at ambient temperature. In the same way, the desired active phase loading was achieved by applying successive impregnations followed by calcination at 550 °C, in air atmosphere for 30 min. Finally, the carriers were sintered in a furnace for 1 h at 950 °C. Carriers with different NiO:Al₂O₃ weight ratios ranging from 10% to 25% were prepared from one to three successive impregnations. The final prepared samples are proposed in the following figures.

Figure 5: Fe₂₀γAl (left), Ni₁₈αAl (center), Ilmenite (right)

Figure 6: Tierga ore (left), Iron-Manganese-Titanium based oxygen carriers (center), Manganese-Iron Oxygen carriers (right)

The above reported oxygen carriers were characterized with the equipment proposed in figure 7.

Figure 7: Characterization apparatus used in the project GTCLC-NEG

The results of the characterization process are reported in table 5. A summary of the main results is presented in table 6 and the progress of the activities in table 7.

Table 5: Main characteristics of the oxygen carrier samples prepared and characterized at the Instituto de Carboquimica.

	Fe20 γ Al	Ni18 α Al	Mn66Fe-Ti7	Mn-Ti20	Ilmenite	Fe-ore
Metal oxide content (wt.%)	20	18	100	93	80	76.5
XRD	Fe ₂ O ₃ α -Al ₂ O ₃	NiO NiAl ₂ O ₄ γ - Al ₂ O ₃	(Mn _{0.66} Fe _{0.34}) ₂ O ₃ (Mn _{0.66} Fe _{0.34}) ₃ O ₄ TiO ₂	Mn ₃ O ₄ Mn ₂ TiO ₄	Fe ₂ TiO ₅ Fe ₂ O ₃ TiO ₂	Fe ₂ O ₃ SiO ₂ CaO MgO
R _{OC,theor} (%)	2.0	3.8	9.5	6.2	4.0	2.5
R _{OC,exp} (%)	1.6	<3.8	9.5	4.7	3.3	2.5
Rate index, CH ₄ (%/min)	8.8	25.9	4.5	2.3	0.6	2.0
ρ_s (kg/m ³)	3950	2500	4940	4850	4100	4210
C.S. (N)	1.5	4.1	1.9	3.7	3.8	5.8
ϵ_p (%)	50.5	42.5	30.0	20.0	1.2	26.3
S _{BET} (m ² /g)	39.1	7.0	<1	<1	<1	1.4

Table 6: Summary of results

Type of result	Description
1. Main scientific and/or technological achievements	<p>- oxygen carrier using alumina as support have proved good performance at high temperature, especially when using nickel as an oxygen carrier</p> <p>- these have performed mainly better than mixed metals</p> <p>- they have several advantages:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - reduced attrition - higher reactivity - higher oxygen transport capacity <p>When the materials produced were tested and characterized with a thermogravimetric balance at a constant temperature of 1000°C (see figure 8), a clear reduction of slope was shown in the first reduction respect to the second one. This is due to the formation of nickel aluminate which is less reactive than nickel oxide.</p>
2. Main innovation outputs (if applicable)	The techniques used to prepare the oxygen carriers have been all developed and patented by the Insituto de Carboquimica in Zaragoza, Spain.

	This has been one of the first research works on mixed metal oxides preparation and characterization.
3. Contribution to the state of the art	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nickel oxide loaded on support has never been tested at very high temperatures; - the behavior of pure nickel oxide and the formation of nickel aluminate at those temperatures is a phenomenon which has been firstly detected during these experiments.
4. Scientific and/or technological quality of the results	A publication has been developed on ilmenite characterization, see [1].

Table 7: Progress of the activities summary

Type of result	Progress of the activities
1. Main research / innovation	<p>Main innovation regards the science of materials. It is important to produce properly the synthetic oxygen carriers to understand for example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the interaction between the support (alumina) and the metal oxide which is loaded on the support. This becomes a key aspect when nickel based oxygen carriers are produced. - the structure of the material (both for synthetic and natural oxygen carriers) and its composition in terms of main and trace components. - oxygen vacancies and lattice oxygen migration processes.
2. Researcher's training	<p>The researcher training was made on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Main catalyst preparation processes as reported in the book of Krijn P. de Jong “Synthesis of Solid Catalysts” [10] - During the stay the researcher was also trained on oxygen carrier characterization and analysis. We remember the training course on “Advanced Training on Gas Sorption with Dr. Martin Thomas”. Delivered at ICB-CSIC - Also the course on LAMMPS software and the possibility to used in ICB-CISC software for DFT analysis and the software “Materials Studio” of Biovia, which was available at CSIC together with the use of the supercomputer TRUENO (now DRAGO) it was a nice opportunity to get more into deep of materials analysis. - In this sense also a course delivered by CSIC on RSTUDIO software and in particular on “Técnicas Avanzadas de Machine Learning y su aplicación (con R) en Investigación Científica” was useful to understand how to further analyse big data to optimize oxygen carrier analysis, as also stated by latest works published in Chalmers university, see [11].

3. Transfer of knowledge	The researcher had already learned imbibition at SINTEF during his BRISK2 projects on the loading of zeolites with iron oxide catalyst. Besides this he had also characterized catalysts in the past and was expert on BET analysis applied to charcoal, alumina and zeolites.
4. Difficulties or problems encountered; how they were solved (please report any deviations from the Description of the Action -DoA- in section 5)	To check the purity of the material and the correct execution of the preparation methods the produced oxygen carriers were characterized through thermogravimetric analysis to understand oxygen transport capacity and material reactivity. No difficulties or problems were encountered.

WP2: Batch Fluidized Bed (FB) reactors tests (February 2022 – December 2022)

The high temperature tests were performed in a batch fluidized bed reactor. This reactor was realized and tested for the first time during the GTCLC-NEG Marie Curie Project. The reactor was made of Kanthal, an alloy made of FeCrAl, which allowed to reach high temperatures during the oxidation and reduction steps. The dimensions of the reactor are shown in Figure 8. The final batch plant layout instead it is shown in Figure 9.

REACTOR DIMENSIONS

(*data are in millimeters)

Figure 8: Reactor dimensions (mm).

Figure 9: Layout of the batch fluidized bed reactor system.

Several redox cycles were done at different temperatures: 950°C, 1000°C, 1050°C, 1100°C, 1150°C and 1200°C. In the layout we see that the reacting gases enter from the bottom of the reactor. Reduction was performed for a time of about 2 minutes with CH₄ diluted in N₂ and steam. Water vapor avoids carbon deposition below the distributor plate. The subsequent oxidation was done in air until the oxygen concentration which is typical of air is reached, typically about 10 minutes. Between the reduction and oxidation steps, the gas is switched for 2 minutes to 100% nitrogen, which is used as a purging gas to avoid the mixture of combustible gases with oxygen. The gas velocity is maintained constant at 0.20 m/s in the fluidized bed reactor. The gases flows are regulated by a series of flowmeters.

Gas concentration (CH₄, CO₂, CO, H₂ and O₂) are measured with different systems located at the exit of the reactor.

Inside the reactor about 300 g of oxygen carrier are placed. The pressure drop inside the reactor is monitored with two water columns. At the end of every test, three samples were collected:

- about 25 g from the bed (which is also weighted right after the reactor is opened);
- a sample in the horizontal pipe;
- a sample in the condenser.

To evaluate attrition rate of the oxygen carrier, particles with a particle size below 40 µm were accounted for both in samples in the horizontal pipe and condenser. Particles from samples taken from the bed (~25 g) were characterized to evaluate the evolution of their physic-chemical properties with the high-temperature redox cycles.

RESULTS

Tests performed with Fe₂O₃ γ Al

Oxygen carrier performance during CH₄ combustion tests

The results obtained with iron oxygen carrier (Fe₂O₃γAl) are shown in Figure 10. As it can be seen at lower temperatures together with the combustion products: carbon dioxide and water vapor also hydrogen and carbon monoxide are produced. These are products of incomplete combustion and their production is mainly due to reforming. With the increase of the temperature both reduction and oxidation reaction happen more rapidly and also more completely and carbon monoxide and hydrogen decrease their concentrations.

Figure 10: Gases analysis at different temperatures with oxygen carrier Fe₂O₃γAl

Oxygen carrier characterization

The main physic-chemical properties of the oxygen carrier particles reacted at different temperatures were compared to the analysis performed for the fresh material shown in the deliverable D1.2 on oxygen carrier characterization. The most important results obtained for iron are presented in the following paragraphs.

a) Solids density analysis

Figure 11 shows the evolution of the skeletal density of the solids. The skeletal density slightly increased with the reacting temperature, which suggest that the crystalline structure of the solid may have changed differently depending on the temperature.

Figure 11: Solids density analysis

b) XRD analysis

The crystalline compounds in the solids were identified by XRD analysis; see Figure 12. The main active compound was Fe₂O₃. No iron-aluminates were identified. Therefore, most of iron could be regenerated, and no deactivation of the material could be anticipated. In fact, combustion performance improved with temperature; see Figure 3.

Regarding the alumina, peaks with higher intensity was found for reacted samples. This fact suggest that the crystallinity of the support increased during the reaction, which could be promoted by the Fe-Al interaction during the redox cycles following the reactions:

Figure 12: XRD analysis of Fe₂OAl samples reacted at different temperatures. Raw material (1st up), Bed at 950°C (2nd up), Bed at 1000°C (3rd up), Bed at 1050°C (4th up).

c) Reactivity analysis

The reactivity analysis of the samples was performed in an atmospheric TGA with 15 % CH₄ at 950 °C; see Figure 13. In general, reactivity was unchanged after redox cycling at different temperatures. Interestingly, a decrease in the reactivity of the oxygen carrier can be noted in reacted samples reacted at 1050 °C. Additional analysis to the solid samples were carried out to determine the cause of the low reactivity of samples reacted at 1050 °C.

Figure 13: Reactivity analysis of the samples

d) SEM analysis

The appearance of the particles can be observed by SEM analysis; see Figures 14 and 15. The examination of the particles showed that the integrity of the particles could be maintained at the macro-scale in particles reacted at 950 and 1000 °C. Thus, no major cracks could be identified, which suggest that the thermal stress suffered by these particles was low. However, some internal cracks are observed in particles reacted at 1050 °C, which may compromise the mechanical behavior of this material at such high temperature. At the micro-scale, it could be observed that the fresh particles were formed mainly by small porous, which increased in size with the temperature in reacted particles. Then, the solid structure showed some sinterization when particles reacted at a higher temperature. This fact could justify the low reactivity of particles reacted at 1050 °C. This behavior could be conditioned by a notorious sinterization of particles in the fluidized bed at this temperature.

Figure 14: Solids SEM analysis

Figure 15: Solids SEM analysis, particles cut in section

The internal appearance of the particles also showed some differences depending on the reacting temperature. It can be observed a nucleus-shell structure in fresh particles and particles reacted at 950 and 1000 °C. This pattern disappears in particles reacted at 1050 °C. A SEM-EDX line-scan shows that iron was accumulated in the core of the particles, and some migration to the external surface was observed with the reacting temperature (see figure 16). Eventually, a homogeneous distribution of iron in the particles was achieved at 1050 °C.

Figure 16: SEM-EDX line-scan analysis.

e) Attrition analysis

Fine particles below 40 μm diameter were found in different solid fractions extracted during the tests of the oxygen carrier in the fluidized bed. Figure 17 shows that some fines were elutriated and recovered downstream the reactor. However, most of fine particles remained in the fluidized bed. This fact was confirmed by the particle size distribution analysis of solids in the bed; see Figure 18. Although the mean particle size barely changed (235 μm for fresh vs. 233 μm for reacted particles), it can be seen an appreciable generation of particles below 100 μm in reacted particles. Taking in consideration these results together the appearance of particles in SEM analysis, it can be deduced that particles suffered of some abrasion, but breakage of particles is not detectable.

Figure 17: Attrition analysis

Figure 18: Solids particles diameter of fresh particles and particles reacted at 1050 °C.

f) Mechanical strength

The crushing strength values of the reacted particles at different temperatures are shown in Figure 19. These results are in agreement with the evaluation of the particles done above by other characterization techniques. Thus, the crushing strength barely changed in particles reacted at 950 and 1000 °C; but it showed a relevant decrease for the particles reacted at 1050 °C. The crushing strength of particles reacted at 1050 °C was about 0,5 N, which is below the threshold limit of 1 N usually considered for a proper operation of oxygen carrier particles in a fluidized bed reactor.

Figure 19: Crushing strength of the particles

Test performed with Ni18 α Al

In a second experimental campaign, it was chosen to use Nickel as oxygen carrier. For this reason, it was tested the Ni18 α Al material.

Oxygen carrier performance during CH₄ combustion tests

With the Ni18Al material, we observed a high fraction of hydrogen in the product gases –see Figure 20-, which was due to the high catalytic effect of nickel on the steam methane reforming.

Figure 20: Redox cycles at 1000°C with Ni18Al oxygen carrier

The uncompleted oxidation of hydrogen can be due to the fact that fresh particles calcined at high temperature caused the generation of a form of nickel-aluminate. This form is less reactive than nickel oxide. Also during the reduction step it takes more time to completely reduce the oxygen carrier and the two minutes set previously did not perform effectively following the reaction:

For this reason, as a first solution it was thought to perform reduction with hydrogen for a longer period:

The reduction of nickel aluminate decreased the presence of this compound after its oxidation, and the problem disappeared momentarily at high temperatures because they were sufficient to completely reduce the nickel and avoid the formation of a high fraction of nickel aluminate during the oxidation. However, this effect could not be maintained during the consecutive redox cycles, and eventually high fraction of hydrogen was again observed. This phenomenon has been studied also in previous works performed at ICB-CSIC. We refer in particular to the thesis of Cristina Dueso⁸, which is based on the kinetics of the reaction between nickel oxide and various hydrocarbons (like methane). Thus, nickel was oxidized mainly to NiO by the following reaction:

However, a fraction of nickel could be converted into nickel aluminate in the presence of alumina by:

Thus, NiAl₂O₄ could be accumulated in the particles during consecutive redox cycles, which was promoted by as the reacting temperature increased. As an example, an overview of the product gas profiles during redox cycles at 950 and 1150 °C are shown in Figures 21 and 22. It was observed an improvement of the combustion with the temperature, which may be related to an increase of the reactivity of nickel aluminate with temperature.

Figure 21: Redox reactions at 950°C

⁸ Dueso, C. (2010). Combustión de gases con separación inherente de CO₂ mediante transportadores de oxígeno basados en NiO.

Figure 22: Redox reactions at temperature of 1150°C

The existence of nickel bonded to alumina was proved using TGA analysis. Thus, the low reactive nickel aluminate fraction increased with the reaction temperature in the fluidized bed reactor. But a higher temperature also improved the reactivity of nickel aluminate. This fact suggest that this material could achieve a suitable high reactivity for PCLC process even though nickel aluminate was formed.

3.2.2. Attrition behavior of Ni18Al

Attrition measures of the Ni18Al oxygen carrier are presented in Figure 23. Similar to what was found for the Fe20Al material, fine particles below 40 μm diameter were found in different solid fractions extracted during the tests of the oxygen carrier in the fluidized bed. Some fines were elutriated and recovered downstream the reactor. However, most of fine particles remained in the fluidized bed. The fraction of fine particles showed a relevant increase when the reacting temperature increased from 950 °C to 1100 °C. Then, this increase was of low relevance when temperature was increased up to 1200 °C. The analysis of the fines produced indicates that this material showed an improved performance compared to the Fe20Al material. Thus, fines produced at 1200 °C with Ni18Al are comparable to fines produced with the Fe20Al material at the lowest temperature tested, i.e. 950 °C. This fact makes that the Ni18Al material could be considered as a promising oxygen carrier to be used in the PCLC process.

Figure 23: Nickel attrition measures

A summary of the results and the progress of the activities is shown in Tables 8 and 9, respectively.

Table 8: Summary of results

Type of result	Description
1. Main scientific and/or technological achievements	<p>The batch experiments were performed in a new type of reactor. This was tested for the first time at the Instituto de Carboquímica (ICB-CISC). The batch reactor was made of a particular alloy named Kanthal, which is an alloy of FeCrAl. This alloy can withstand very high temperatures, up to 1300°C. The reactor was used to select optimal oxygen carriers which had the following characteristics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - did not agglomerate in the bed even at very high temperatures - avoided sintering at high temperatures - did not produce too much fines due to attrition which increased its effect at the increase of temperature <p>At the end of the batch tests we achieved the following relevant scientific results:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - nickel based oxygen carrier could withstand temperatures up to 1200°C continuing working with high conversion efficiency; - reforming was reduced in favor of combustion reactions - no agglomeration, sintering was measured for nickel based oxygen carrier - reduced attrition was also experienced. - Attrition generally increased with the increase of temperature.

2. Main innovation outputs (if applicable)	During the experiments conducted in this workpackage it was found a particular range of conditions of temperature in which the reforming action during the combustion process was reduced and the combustion efficiency was greater. This range was for temperatures comprised between 1100°C and 1200°C.
3. Contribution to the state of the art	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - optimal ranges of temperatures was found to operate a fluidized bed combustor to be coupled to a gas turbine; - it was possible to effectively work at temperatures of about 1200°C - low attrition and agglomeration and sintering were noted for nickel based oxygen carriers; - the plant concept was proved to be feasible at a pilot scale.
4. Scientific and/or technological quality of the results	<p>With these results a paper has been prepared and it is going to be submitted in the next months.</p> <p>Also the results of modeling of the batch reactor have been presented in a Keynote speech by the Marie Curie Individual Fellow at the “Applied Energy Symposium : MIT A+B, 2022” at the MIT in Boston.</p>

Table 9: Progress of the activities summary

Type of result	Progress of the activities
1. Main research / innovation	The batch experiments were performed in a new type of reactor, which could withstand high temperatures (in the order of 1200°C).
2. Researcher's training	<p>The researcher was trained on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Safety procedures to manage Nickel oxides compounds - Safety procedures to work with flammable and explosive compounds (like methane and hydrogen) - Correct use of individual protection devices; - Mounting and dismounting a batch reactor - Managing a Labview data acquisition system - Managing different gas analysers and the relative connections and piping - Oxygen carrier characterization and analysis - Mass and energy balances calculations (including carbon balances calculations). - Training on CFD of multiphase process with the software MFIX
3. Transfer of knowledge	The researcher transferred his knowledge on CFD modeling of multiphase processes. The researcher was also opportunely trained on this field to increase his know how and skills.
4. Difficulties or problems encountered; how they were solved (please report any	The technological problem experienced in this experimental campaign was linked with the insurgence of reforming instead of combustion reactions. This was managed by

deviations from the Description of the Action -DoA- in section 5)	changing reduction period duration and also the temperature at which the process was performed. Also it was difficult to achieve pressurized conditions with the available equipment in that case experimental data were used to calibrate a CFD model which could be used as a digital twin of the plant and provide realistic data.
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WP3: Modelling work (February 2022 – June 2023)

PARTICLE MODEL

The particle modeling of the oxygen carriers produced and characterized in WP 1 is based on two publications realized at the Instituto de Carboquímica, CSIC, see [12, 13]. These works are based also on the theory developed by Levenspiel [14] when speaking of reactions catalyzed by solids and the pore diffusion resistance combined with surface kinetics. The reaction of a solid oxygen carrier with a fuel gas, e.g., CH₄, is classified as a non-catalytic gas-solid reaction. In this case, the resistance to pore diffusion is not relevant, and chemical reaction on the gas-solid interphase is the limiting step of the reaction. The kinetic model assumes that the particle is composed by small grains of the active phase, which may be spherical or have a plate-like geometry; see Figure 24. In both cases, the reaction progress following a shrinking core model.

Figure 24: spherical (a) and plate-like (b) geometries for the active phase in the oxygen carrier particles.

In this project, we focused the particle model on the most interesting oxygen carrier that we have tested, which is Ni₁₈Al. This material was prepared by impregnating nickel on porous alumina particles. The preparation method caused that the active phase (NiO) was deposited in a thin layer on the porous structure of alumina. Therefore, NiO grains are recognized to have a plate like geometry. For this kind of geometry, the governing equations for the particle model reaction based on the Shrinking Core Model (SCM) are as follows:

$$X_r = \frac{1}{\tau^*} t \quad (1)$$

$$\tau = \frac{\tau^*}{0.8^{1/3}} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dX_r}{dt} = \frac{1}{\tau} \quad (3)$$

$$\tau = \frac{1}{k_r c_g^n} \quad (4)$$

$$k_r = k_{r,0} e^{-E_a/RT} \quad (5)$$

where:

- t is time (s)

- X_r is the solid conversion
- τ^* is the time for complete solid conversion in the current experiment, with the fraction of Ni as NiO being 0.8 (s)
- τ is the time for complete solid conversion assuming all Ni was as NiO (s)
- C_g is the partial pressure of the reacting gas, CH₄ in this case (mol/m³)
- n is the reaction order (-)
- k_r is the kinetic constant (m³ⁿmol⁻ⁿs⁻¹)
- $k_{r,0}$ is the pre-exponential factor of the kinetic constant (m³ⁿmol⁻ⁿs⁻¹)
- E_a is the activation energy (J/mol)
- R_g is the ideal gas constant (=8.314 J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹)

The kinetic parameters were derived through experimental tests in a pressurized thermogravimetric analyzer (PTGA) at the laboratories of Instituto de Carboquímica, ICB-CSIC.

In particular, we consider the R_o of NiO (oxygen transport capacity of nickel oxide), the nickel oxide content in the oxygen carrier (X_{NiO}), and the oxygen transport capacity of the material (R_{oc}), which is derived by multiplying the oxygen transport capacity of nickel oxide for the content of nickel oxide in the oxygen carrier. In this case:

$$R_{oc} = X_{NiO} * R_o = 0.18 * 0.2 = 0.036 \quad (6)$$

Thus, the oxygen carrier conversion may be calculated based on the mass of the sample (m) and the maximum mass variation, which is calculated by multiplying the mass of the oxidized sample (m_{ox}) by the oxygen transport capacity of the oxygen carrier (R_{oc}).

$$X_r = \frac{m_{ox} - m}{R_{oc} m_{ox}} \quad (7)$$

EXPERIMENTAL CAMPAIGN

In this work, the effect of reacting pressure on the reaction kinetics will be determined in a PTGA. First, a calibration test was performed to evaluate the effect of the total pressure on the reacting conditions in the PTGA. Figure 25 shows several calibration tests using the calcium oxalate method. It was observed that the registered temperature in the 400-600 °C interval was affected by the total pressure. Thus, the reacting temperature was corrected in this interval as Table 10 shows.

Figure 25: Calcium oxalate decomposition at different total pressure values in the PTGA.

Table 10: Adjusted temperature in the PTGA (in the range of 400-600°C)

15 bar	-18°C
10 bar	0°C
5 bar	+6°C
1 bar	+31°C

Preliminary tests were performed by varying the mass sample or the gas flow to evaluate the effect of diffusional effects on the observable reaction rate. Then, tests at different reacting temperature, total pressure and CH₄ partial pressure values were performed using the Ni18 α Al as the oxygen carrier. The tests performed are reported in Table 11. Note that when the total pressure was varied, two different series were carried out: first varying the CH₄ concentration in order to maintain constant the CH₄ partial pressure; and second, with a constant CH₄ concentration, but in this case the CH₄ partial pressure varied with the total pressure.

Table 11: Experimental campaign performed at the PTGA

Qt (l/h)	m (mg)	T(°C)	Pt (atm)	%CH4	%CO2	%N2	Air	PCH4	
240	30	475	10	10	3	19	78	100	0.3
240	50	475	10	10	3	19	78	100	0.3
240	70	475	10	10	3	19	78	100	0.3
240	50	475	10	10	3	19	78	100	0.3
200	50	475	10	10	3	19	78	100	0.3
175	50	475	10	10	3	19	78	100	0.3
240	50	500	10	10	3	19	78	100	0.3
240	50	475	10	10	3	19	78	100	0.3
240	50	450	10	10	3	19	78	100	0.3
240	50	425	10	10	3	19	78	100	0.3
240	50	475	1	30	19	51	100	0.3	
240	50	475	5	6	19	75	100	0.3	
240	50	475	10	3	19	78	100	0.3	
240	50	475	15	2	19	79	100	0.3	
240	50	475	1	3	19	78	100	0.03	
240	50	475	5	3	19	78	100	0.15	
240	50	475	10	3	19	78	100	0.3	
240	50	475	15	3	19	78	100	0.45	

Figure 26 shows an example of mass variation for consecutive redox cycles varying the reacting temperature. The variation of the sample mass corresponded to the oxygen depletion during reduction or its replenishment during oxidation:

Figure 26: Mass variation for consecutive redox cycles varying the reacting temperature

The effect of the total pressure, the partial pressure of CH₄ and the reacting temperature on the reaction kinetics of NiO reduction was determined by PTGA tests with the Ni18αAl material. Thus, the reaction order at 5 and 15 atm was determined by considering the variation of the reaction rate when the molar fraction of CH₄ was varied. Thus, the reaction order may be obtained by linearizing Eq. (4):

$$\ln(\tau) = -\ln(k_r) - n \ln(C_g) \quad (8)$$

Figure 27 shows a plot of $\ln(\tau)$ vs. $\ln(C_g)$. The slope of the linear fitting is the reaction order. It can be seen that the n value barely changed with the total pressure from 0.74 to 0.79. An average value of $n=0.76$ may be taken. The y-intercept is $\ln(k_r)$; then k_r was 0.011 and 0.0067 $\text{m}^{2.28}\text{mol}^{-0.76}\text{s}^{-1}$ at 5 and 15 atm, respectively.

Figure 27: Effect of the CH₄ concentration, C_g , on the τ parameter at 5 and 15 atm. $T = 779$ K.

Therefore, the apparent kinetic constant, k_r , was affected by the total pressure. Several tests at different total pressures were performed at 779 K and 3 vol.% CH₄ in the PTGA. The determined reaction rates, dX_r/dt , decreased when the total pressure increased from 1 to 5 atm. Then, the reaction rate progressively increased with the total pressure at 10 and 15 atm; see Figure 28. This behavior was related to a decrease of the apparent kinetic constant, k_r . Figure 28 shows the variation of k_r with the total pressure.

Figure 28: Variation of the reaction rate and the apparent kinetic constant with the total pressure. $T = 779$ K.

To determine the effect of the total pressure on the apparent kinetic constant, additional tests were performed varying the total pressure but maintaining constant the CH₄ partial pressure. Figure 29 shows the evolution of the calculated apparent kinetic constant, k_r , with the total pressure. It was determined that the effect of the decrease in k_r was stronger at low total pressure, and then it was less relevant for elevated pressures. In order to predict the k_r value as a function of the total pressure, the following equation was proposed:

$$k_r(P) = \frac{k_r(P=1\text{atm})}{P_t^d} \quad (9)$$

where d is a fitting parameter to consider the effect of total pressure on the kinetic constant. From the fitting shown in Figure 29, it was determined that $d=0.9$.

Figure 29: Effect of total pressure in the apparent kinetic constant, k_r . $T = 779$ K.

Finally, the effect of the reaction temperature on the kinetic constant was considered. Tests at 10 atm were performed at different temperatures between 729 and 804 K. Figure 30 shows that the apparent kinetic constant increased with temperature. An Arrhenius-type dependency of k_r with temperature was assumed:

$$k_r = k_{r,0} e^{-E_a/(R_g T)} \quad (10)$$

$$\ln(k_r) = \ln(k_{r,0}) - \frac{E_a}{R_g} \frac{1}{T} \quad (11)$$

Thus, the activation energy (E_a) was calculated from the slope of Figure 30, while the pre-exponential factor, $k_{r,0}$, could be calculated from the y-intercept. The calculated values for these parameters were $k_{r,0}(P=10 \text{ atm}) = 204 \text{ m}^{2.28} \text{ mol}^{-0.76} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $E_a = 65.8 \text{ kJ/mol}$. Considering Eq. (9), may be calculated that the pre-exponential factor for 1 atm is $k_{r,0}(P=1 \text{ atm}) = 1.74 \cdot 10^3 \text{ m}^{2.28} \text{ mol}^{-0.76} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Therefore, the following equation was derived to calculate the kinetic constant as a function of the reacting temperature and the total pressure:

$$k_r = \frac{1.74 \cdot 10^3}{P_t^{0.9}} e^{-65800/(R_g T)} \quad (12)$$

Figure 30: Effect of the reacting temperature on the kinetic constant.

0D REACTOR MODEL

A 0D Reactor model has been developed in the Marie Curie project GTCLC-NEG with the following objectives:

- To analyze whether ilmenite ore is a suitable oxygen carrier to burn natural gas in a PCLC unit. In this regard, the poor reactivity exhibited by ilmenite to combust methane at atmospheric pressure discourages the use of this material in CLC processes with natural gas. However, recent studies have shown that pressure could have a positive effect on the reactivity of this oxygen carrier during the methane reduction and air oxidation steps.
- To evaluate which configuration, i.e., DFBC or ICR, is more convenient in terms of a series of relevant design parameters for a PCLC unit such as combustion efficiency, reactor sizing and reactor pressure drop.
- To study whether the use of ilmenite as an oxygen carrier allows an optimal energy integration of the PCLC system. In order to achieve high net electric efficiency values, it is necessary to operate at high pressures (~2 MPa) and temperatures (>1200 °C). In this regard, these high temperatures represent a very ambitious research and technological challenge since the oxygen carrier must maintain adequate physicochemical properties at these conditions and this requirement has not been demonstrated yet with any oxygen carrier in continuous CLC pilot plants during long-term experimental campaigns. However, PCLC technology can be also implemented in other applications, such as heat production, in which such high temperatures are not required and the projects can also become profitable from an economic point of view. Specifically, in this work an energy analysis of a CLC system, designed under DFBC and ICR configurations at atmospheric and pressurized (0.5 MPa) conditions, has been carried out for two different applications of heat generation: production of domestic hot water (DHW) and process steam.

The fuel reactor was considered to operate in bubbling or turbulent regime depending on the reactor configuration selected, i.e., ICR or DFBC, respectively. The theoretical model for the fuel reactor considered the main processes affecting the reaction of methane with the oxygen carrier, such as reactor fluid dynamics, the reactivity of the oxygen carrier and the reaction mechanism.

A fluid dynamic study was done based on generalized map of gas/solid contacting. Figure 31 shows the map of fluidizing regimes for several total pressure values, ranging from 0.1 to 1.5 MPa, as a function of the gas velocity and particle size for ilmenite particles with density 3900 kg/m³.

$$Re_{mf} = \sqrt{27.2^2 + 0.0408Ar} - 27.2 \quad (13)$$

$$\text{Re}_t = \text{Ar}^{1/3} \left[\frac{18}{\text{Ar}^{2/3}} + \frac{2.335 - 1.744\phi_s}{\text{Ar}^{1/6}} \right]^{-1} \quad (14)$$

$$\text{Re}_c = 0.74 \text{Ar}^{0.426} \quad (15)$$

$$\text{Re}_{se} = 1.68 \text{Ar}^{0.469} \quad (16)$$

Fig. 31. Fluidization regime in the flow map for the fuel reactor burning CH_4 with ilmenite particles. Continuous lines/symbols: reactor inlet conditions. Dashed lines/symbols: reactor outlet conditions. Selected conditions for bubbling regime (\blacklozenge , \blacklozenge , \blacklozenge , \blacklozenge) or turbulent regime (\blacksquare , \blacksquare , \blacksquare , \blacksquare). Closed symbols: gas velocity constant. Open symbols: cross section constant.

Fluidization in the bubbling regime is considered for gas velocities between u_{mf} and u_c . The transition boundaries for turbulent and fast fluidization regime are defined by u_c and u_{se} , respectively. The gas velocity for the transition between the bubbling, turbulent and fast fluidization decreases as the total pressure increases. In addition, these boundaries are different for the gas at the reactor inlet, mainly CH_4 , or the gas at the reactor outlet, mainly CO_2 and H_2O . Note that the gas velocity increases as the methane is being converted in the fuel reactor, following the expansion given by the chemical reaction between methane and ilmenite:

All these factors must be considered to define the operating conditions of the fuel reactor in both bubbling and turbulent/fast fluidization regime; see Figure 31. Reference conditions at atmospheric pressure were properly selected to evaluate the effect of total pressure on the fuel reactor performance. Bigger particles of ilmenite were considered for the bubbling regime ($d_p = 0.25$ mm) compared to the turbulent regime ($d_p = 0.12$ mm). This fact was motivated by the improved gas conversion for a larger particle size in the bubbling regime, while a higher development of the dilute region is predicted for the turbulent regime as the particle size decreases, which improves the gas conversion. Thus, the gas velocity at the reactor inlet was fixed at 0.32 m/s in the bubbling regime and 1.3 m/s in the turbulent regime.

Figure 32 shows the relation of the gas velocity with the cross section normalized per MW_{th} of thermal input. Thus, in order to have a higher gas velocity in the turbulent regime the cross section per MW_{th} should be decreased. The cross section for the bubbling and turbulent regime is 0.4 and 0.1 $\text{m}^2/\text{MW}_{th}$, respectively. Here, two options have been considered for the design of the fuel reactor at pressurized conditions:

Fig. 32: Relation between design parameters (cross section and solids inventory, m_{FR}) and operating conditions (u_g , ΔP) for the design of the fuel reactor burning CH_4 at different total pressures.

First, the inlet gas velocity was maintained constant at the reference conditions for atmospheric pressure by decreasing the cross section of the reactor. The corresponding cross section for 0.5, 1.0 and 1.5 MPa can be deduced from figure 32. In this case, the turbulent regime is maintained as the total pressure increases, or even a fast fluidization could be reached; see Fig. 31. In addition, the bubbling regime moves towards its upper region, or even turbulent regime can be found at total pressures higher than 1.0 MPa. Interesting is the relation between the total pressure and the pressure drop showed in figure 32. Thus, if the cross section decreases with the total pressure, then the pressure drop should increase to maintain the same solids inventory.

Second, the cross section was maintained constant, which implies a decrease of the gas velocity with the total pressure; see figure 32. Considering the same solids inventory, the pressure drop would be maintained constant with the increase of P_t , being lower than those required for the first option described above. However, there is a risk of moving towards the bubbling region for the condition selected for the turbulent regime at atmospheric pressure; or even defluidization for the condition selected for the bubbling regime. Therefore, a limited evaluation of this option is done in this work.

Additional conditions varying the particle size or the gas velocity as a function of the total pressure could be selected, but a deeper evaluation of the effect of these parameters on the fluidization regime is out of the scope of this work.

The combustion efficiency of natural gas, η_c , was estimated with the theoretical model to evaluate the effect of the total pressure at several operating conditions.

$$\eta_c = \frac{\text{oxygen transferred to the fuel}}{\text{oxygen demanded for the fuel}} \quad (18)$$

First, it was simulated the effect of increasing pressure in a fuel reactor. Thus, figure 33 shows the evolution of the combustion efficiency in an existing fuel reactor when the power was proportionally increased with the pressure. This option should be considered to maintain the gas velocity constant when the total pressure was varied. Thus, the specific cross section (m^2/MW) decreased with P_t , as it was described in figure 32, but the amount of solids should increase to maintain the required specific solids inventory (here 500 kg/MW). As a consequence, the pressure drop (and also the bed height) was increased to values without practical interest (high height to section ratios).

Fig. 33. Effect of total pressure on the combustion efficiency at several fuel reactor temperatures when the cross section is decreased accordingly to the increase of the pressure drop. The relation between the cross section and the pressure drop is also shown. $m_{FR} = 500 \text{ kg/MW}_{th}$; $\phi = 2$.

Results are included in Fig. 33(a) for the bubbling regime and Fig. 33(b) for the turbulent regime. The solids circulation rate and solids inventory were fixed at $3.6 \text{ kg/s per MW}_{th}$, and 500 kg/MW_{th} , respectively. This corresponds to an oxygen carrier-to-fuel ratio of $\phi = 2$. Incomplete combustion was predicted at atmospheric pressure, due to ilmenite is not a suitable oxygen carrier for the methane combustion. The potential of increasing the gas conversion by increasing the solids inventory or the solids circulation rate is limited, and it is not described in this work. The potential of increasing the fuel conversion by increasing the total pressure is analysed. In these cases, the pressure drop should be increased.

Both in the bubbling and turbulent regime the combustion efficiency increased with the reacting temperature due to an increase in the reaction kinetics. However, a relevant decrease in the combustion efficiency was predicted as the total pressure increased in the bubbling regime, even when the reaction rate increases with the total pressure. We conclude that the fluid dynamics variation with total pressure is highly relevant for the negative effect of pressure on the combustion efficiency. The gas conversion in the dense bed is limited due to the mass transfer between bubbles and emulsion phases, but the fraction of solids in the dense bed increases with the total pressure (e.g. from 57 % to 95 % at 0.1 and 1.0 MPa, respectively), which justifies the decrease of gas conversion with pressure. It is also relevant that the reaction rate does not increase as much as would be expected if the negative effect of the total pressure on the kinetics did not exist.

In general, the fuel conversion in the turbulent regime is higher than in the bubbling regime due to the development of the dilute region, which is more efficient converting the fuel gas than the dense bed. In the turbulent regime, the effect of the total pressure on the conversion efficiency shows the same decreasing trend with the total pressure at high temperature, i.e. 1000 and 1100 °C. Again, the main reason is the low efficiency of the dense bed burning the fuel. However, the opposite tendency was predicted at 800 °C, which is related to an improvement in the mass transference rate predicted in the upper part of the dense bed at pressurized conditions. This effect is evident when the dense bed is high and the reaction kinetics is low, i.e. high ΔP and 800 °C. In this case, an improvement of the fuel conversion was predicted with an increase of the total pressure. From results in figure 33, it was deduced that the fuel conversion could be increased at high temperature. However, a safe temperature of 1000 °C would be recommended with ilmenite to avoid agglomerations problems. Therefore, this temperature was selected for the following simulations. In addition, it is not expected an improvement of the fuel conversion by increasing the total pressure when the cross section was correspondingly decreased to maintain the inlet gas velocity constant.

Finally, from the results shown in figure 33, it can be concluded that the pressure drop in the reactor increases considerably as the total pressure increases while maintaining a constant section, which implies the decrease of the specific cross section (m^2/MW). This leads to very high bed heights in the reactor, which would be an insurmountable challenge from a technical point of view.

In order to maintain the pressure drop constant, the specific cross section may be also maintained with pressure; i.e. the pressure to section ratio is not varied. This condition may be achieved either modifying the section of

the reactor or maintaining the fuel flow and power constant with the pressure variation. In this case, the inlet gas velocity may decrease to velocities below u_{mf} or u_c for the bubbling and turbulent conditions, respectively, as the pressure increases; see Figure 31. However, an increase of the pressure up to 0.5 MPa makes possible the maintenance of the fluidization regime. Thus, considering the cross section selected for atmospheric pressure in the bubbling regime of $0.4 \text{ m}^2/\text{MW}$, the combustion efficiency was 73.6 %; see Figure 34. With the same cross section, the inlet gas velocity was reduced by 5 at 0.5 MPa, but the combustion efficiency was increased to 76.7 %. This fact was related to the improvement of the mass transference in the dense bed with the decrease of the gas velocity.

Fig. 34 Effect of the inlet gas velocity on the combustion efficiency for the bubbling and turbulent regimes. The inlet gas velocity was varied changing the cross section of the fuel reactor, and its relation with the pressure drop is also shown. $P_t = 0.5 \text{ MPa}$, $T_{FR} = 1000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $m_{FR} = 500 \text{ kg}/\text{MW}_{th}$, $\phi = 2$. Solid and dashed lines correspond to the values of combustion efficiency and cross section, respectively. Blue color is referred to bubbling regime and red color to turbulent regime.

From the above simulations, the fuel conversion was relatively low, typically 60–80 % at 0.5 MPa and 1000 °C. Ilmenite is known to be an oxygen carrier with low reactivity towards CH_4 , and both atmospheric and pressurized conditions were not suitable to achieve complete conversion of natural gas. A sensitivity analysis on the kinetic constant was done in order to estimate the required oxygen carrier reactivity to achieve 99 % combustion efficiency with $m_{FR} = 500 \text{ kg}/\text{MW}_{th}$. At 0.1 MPa, the kinetic constant should be multiplied by 6 and 4 in the bubbling ($0.4 \text{ m}^2/\text{MW}_{th}$) and turbulent regime ($0.1 \text{ m}^2/\text{MW}_{th}$), respectively. At 0.5 MPa, the multiplying factor should be 8 and 4.5.

A deeper evaluation of the effect of the particle size or gas velocity on the combustion efficiency is out of the scope of this work. However, the optimization of operating conditions considering these parameters and the flow map in figure 31 is encouraged for future works. Although the possible benefits of increasing the pressure on the fuel conversion has not been confirmed both in bubbling and turbulent regimes, some advantages may be still expected from an energy point of view. These possible benefits are evaluated in the next section.

Energy analysis

This work has been completed with an energy analysis carried out with the Aspen HYSYS V12.1 process simulation software of a CLC plant for the production of heat in the form of domestic hot water (DHW) or process steam in which the fuel reactor operates in a bubbling (ICR configuration) or turbulent (DFCB configuration) regime at atmospheric (0.1 MPa) or pressurized conditions (0.5 MPa) using ilmenite as oxygen carrier. Likewise, the presence of a turbo-expander for the production of electrical power from the hot gas stream obtained at the outlet of the air reactor has been analysed. In total, 6 different cases have been studied, see Table 1. In order to perform this analysis, the previously mentioned CH_4 combustion efficiency values have been considered. These results were obtained with the model developed by Abad et al. [39] when the

temperature in the fuel reactor was 1000 °C, the inventory of ilmenite in this reactor was 500 kg/MW_{th}, and the oxygen carrier-to-fuel ratio, i.e., parameter ϕ , was 2. This model also provides other important parameters for the process, such as the operating temperature in the air reactor and the pressure drop in the fuel reactor. 1 MW of thermal power has been taken as a reference for all the cases analyzed.

Table 12: Process simulation cases. Definitions and model outputs.

	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6
FR regime	Bubbling	Bubbling	Turbulent	Turbulent	Bubbling	Turbulent
Pressure (MPa)	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.1	0.1
Turboexpander	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No
T_{FR} (°C)				1000		
Input thermal power (MW _{th})				1		
CH₄ combustion efficiency (%)	76.7	76.7	78.7	78.7	73.6	84.4
Oxygen carrier-to-fuel ratio, ϕ				2		
Solids inventory in the FR (kg/MW _{th})				500		
T_{AR} (°C)	1035	1035	1035	1035	1038	1041
Pressure drop FR, ΔP_{FR} (kPa)	12	12	48	48	12	48

Figure 35 shows the process flow diagram of the CLC plant for one of the studied configurations, in particular, the one in which both reactors operate at pressurized conditions (0.5 MPa) and a turbo-expander is installed at the outlet of the air reactor (Case 1 or 3). In this CLC plant, the methane and air streams fed to the fuel and air reactors are preheated in a series of heat exchangers (HX₁-HX₃) used to cool the pure CO₂ stream produced at the outlet of the fuel reactor after each compression stage. Once preheated, both currents are pressurized through their corresponding compressors. In Cases 5 and 6, evaluated at atmospheric pressure, the compressors are replaced by a blower, in the case of the methane stream, and by a fan, in the case of the air stream. An additional air stream is sent to an air separation unit (ASU) to produce the amount of pure oxygen required to burn in the O₂ polishing unit the methane that is not converted in the fuel reactor. This unit has a heat exchanger (HX₇) to recover the heat generated in the combustion of the unburned methane. Downstream of the O₂ polishing unit, two heat exchangers (HX₄-HX₅) are installed to use the energy content of the fuel reactor outlet stream, and a water recovery unit is next located to remove this compound and obtain a pure CO₂ stream. The CO₂ stream is then compressed by a series of compressors. These compressors operate with a pressure ratio between inlet and outlet of 5. In the pressurized cases, two compressors are installed in series, whereas a third compressor is included in Cases 5 and 6 at atmospheric pressure. In all cases, the final properties of the compressed CO₂ stream are 12.5 MPa and 35 °C. The gaseous stream coming out of the air reactor passes through a heat exchanger (HX₆) that recovers heat for the production of DHW or process steam. In Cases 1 and 3, where a turboexpander is considered, the inlet temperature at this piece of equipment is 732 °C. The outlet temperature and pressure of the turbo-expander are 439.8 °C and 0.1 MPa, respectively. In addition, at the outlet of the turbo-expander, another heat exchanger (HX₉) has been installed in order to maximize the heat recovery from the depleted air stream by cooling up to 150 °C. In cases where the turbo-expander is not included, the outlet temperature of the HX₆ unit is also 150 °C. Finally, Fig. 5 shows the heating process of the cold water stream ($T_{in} = 45$ °C, $P_{in} = 0.1$ MPa) through the heat exchangers to obtain the corresponding stream of DHW or process steam. In the case of the DHW stream, the final values of temperature and pressure are 90 °C and 0.1 MPa, respectively, whereas the process stream is produced at 350 °C and 4 MPa.

	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6
$W_{\text{turboexpander}}$ (kW _e)	98.9	0	98.9	0	0	0
Electric power output (kW _e)	98.9	0	98.9	0	0	0
Electric power balance (kW _e)	-48.8	-147.7	-46.9	-145.8	-66.3	-68.9
Thermal power						
HX ₄ (kW _{th})	70.6	70.6	70.6	70.6	31.8	31.8
HX ₅ (kW _{th})	109.1	109.1	109.1	109.1	108.9	108.9
HX ₆ (kW _{th})	106.6	299.2	106.6	299.2	301.1	301.1
HX ₇ (kW _{th})	214.1	214.1	196.0	196.0	242.8	143.3
HX ₈ (kW _{th})	426.6	426.6	445.6	445.6	306.7	404.9
HX ₉ (kW _{th})	93.6	0	93.6	0	0	0
Thermal power output (kW _{th})	1020.5	1119.5	1021.5	1120.4	991.3	990.0
Energy applications						
DHW mass flow (kg/h)	1044.0	1144.9	1045.0	1145.9	1014.0	1012.7
Steam mass flow (kg/h)	67.7	74.3	67.8	74.3	65.8	65.7
Total energy balance (kW)	971.7	971.8	974.6	974.7	925.1	921.2

The heat generated in the CLC plant comes from the outlet gas streams of the fuel (HX₄ and HX₅) and air (HX₆ and HX₉) reactors, the O₂ polishing unit (HX₇), and the exothermic reactions that take place in the air reactor between air and the oxygen carrier (HX₈). Firstly, the heat exchanged in the HX₄ is higher for the cases at pressurized conditions than for the ones at atmospheric pressure, since the latent heat of condensation of the water generated in the fuel reactor can be used when the CLC unit operates under pressure. For all the cases, the outlet temperatures of the O₂ polishing unit, HX-5 and HX-4 are 1000 °C, 350 °C and 130 °C, respectively. Secondly, the heat exchanged in the HX-6 unit is lower in Cases 1 and 3, in which the turbo-expander is included, since the outlet temperature in this heat exchanger in these cases is higher (732 °C) than in the other cases (150 °C). Thirdly, the heat generated in the O₂ polishing unit (HX-7) depends on the methane conversion degree achieved in the CLC plant using ilmenite as oxygen carrier. In this regard, the higher the CH₄ combustion efficiency value, the lower the heat recovered in the O₂ polishing unit. The heat generated in the air reactor (HX-8) is higher at pressurized conditions and in all the cases it is the main energy source for the production of DHW or process steam. Finally, 93.6 kW_{th} are recovered in Cases 1 and 3 from the heat exchanger (HX₉) located downstream of the turbo-expander. The highest amounts of thermal energy are produced in Cases 2 and 4. In both cases, the working pressure is 0.5 MPa and there is no generation of electrical power through a turbo-expander. On the contrary, the worst results in terms of thermal power output are obtained in Cases 5 and 6 at atmospheric pressure. In terms of DHW and process steam, the mass flow values vary between 1012.7 and 1145.9 kg H₂O/h and between 65.7 and 74.3 kg steam/h, respectively. From a global energy point of view, that is, taking into account the electric power balance, it can be concluded that the energy efficiency achieved in the pressurized cases (Cases 1–4) is slightly higher than that obtained in the cases performed atmospheric pressure, fundamentally because at pressurized conditions it is possible to take advantage of the latent heat of condensation of the water generated in the fuel reactor. In contrast, the fluidization regime of the fuel reactor, i.e., bubbling or turbulent, has a negligible effect on the energy analysis when the CLC unit operates at 0.5 MPa.

The results presented in this work intend to provide some guidelines to analyze the potential of PCLC technology for the production of heat from natural gas with special emphasis on the configuration/design of the fuel reactor and the energy integration of the continuous PCLC unit. This study has

been carried out considering an ilmenite ore as oxygen carrier, but it could be applied to any other material. To complete this analysis of PCLC technology, it is recommended to carry out a detailed economic study that includes capital expenditures (reactors, turbomachinery, heat exchangers, etc.), operating costs (natural gas, electricity, maintenance and operation, etc.) and income generated.

ASPEN MODEL & CFD ANALYSIS

In figure 36 it is shown the final Aspen Plus model developed during the GTCLC-NEG project and calibrated with proprietary software at Baker Hughes production site in Florence during the secondment.

The first upper part of the scheme is represented by the air reactor; while the lower part is represented by the fuel reactor. We present here the sequence of components:

- the compressor, which grants the pressure necessary to the reactor and also the right mass flow of gas which will result in a velocity inside the reactor capable to grant fast fluidization
- the air reactor where the reduced oxygen carrier enters and the oxidized oxygen carrier exits. The reactor is designed with a Transport Disengaging Height which is higher than the height of the reactor itself this results in the entrainment of the particles inside the reactor which are then collected at the top of the reactor by the cyclone;
- two units cyclone is chosen with default input values used to design it;
- the depleted air exiting the air reactor is then fed to a gas turbine;
- in the same way as for the air reactor, also for the fuel reactor the input gas is moved by a compressor. The gas fed in the fuel reactor is syngas and not air obviously and the mass flow in this case is definitely lower, because of the stoichiometric ratio between air and fuel is about 4 times and also because of the excess air used in this case;
- the interaction between fuel and oxygen carrier is modelled assuming a flow of oxygen carrier which enters the reactor in oxidized state and leaves the reactor in reduced state. The reduction kinetic constants are also reported in Table 14, taken from [15].

Figure 36: Aspen Plus simulation of a 12 MW gas turbine coupled with a Chemical Looping Combustor

- the gases exiting from the reduction reactor are mainly composed by water vapor and carbon dioxide. They will pass through the same cleaning system previously used for the air reactor.

- In this specific plant configuration the gases don't expand in a second gas turbine, but will pass through a HRSG (Heat Recovery Steam Generator) which can provide steam to be expanded in a steam turbine, the HRSG has to be a separate one, respect to that used to recover heat from the gases exiting the air reactor, to avoid mixing again air with carbon dioxide, avoiding the benefits coming from the CLC process itself. This will affect the costs of the entire plant.

Table 14: Oxygen Carrier kinetic Parameters and Reactivity for Reduction [15]

Parameter	H ₂	CO
ρ_m (mol/m ³)	89290	89290
r_g or L (m)	$6.9 * 10^{-7}$	$6.9 * 10^{-7}$
b	1	1
k_0 (mol ¹⁻ⁿ m ³ⁿ⁻² s ⁻¹)	$9.3*10^{-3}$	$5.2*10^{-3}$
E (kJ/mol)	26	25
n	0.5	0.8
q	-0.47	-0.93
dX_r/dt at 0.1 MPa	0.040	0.028
dX_r/dt at 2.1 MPa	0.044	0.019

The CFD modeling was performed with two software:

- MFIX developed by the USDOE National Energy Technology Laboratory (NETL) of Morgantown to deal with multiphase problems. For this sake the Marie Curie Individual Fellow was opportunely trained in two workshops: NETL 2021 Workshop on Multiphase Flow Science and NETL 2022 Workshop on Multiphase Flow Science. The researcher has learned how to write chemical kinetics in Fortran, since the software had a graphical user interface in Python which was interacting with Fortran code.
- Barracuda® software developed by CFPD software which is a robust tool to model also multiphase problems in reactors with 3D, transient behavior in fluid-particle systems. This activity was done in collaboration with a PhD student from Huazhong University of Science and Technology, organized by the Marie Curie Individual Fellow.

In figures 37 and 38 we propose the Fe₂O₃ particle volume fraction during time (Syngas, 1073 K, 10 bar), obtained with Baracuda® software.

Figure 37: Fe₂O₃ particle volume fraction during time (Syngas, 1073 K, 10 bar), obtained with Baracuda® software.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CCPcYeL3NSc&t=3s>

Figure 38: Modeling procedure and results with MFiX software

The modeling results and animations are available in a you tube channel created for the results of the GTCLC-NEG project see⁹.

The summary of the results and the progress of the activities in this workpackage is presented in Tables 14 and 15, respectively.

Table 14: Summary of results

Type of result	Description
1. Main scientific and/or technological achievements	For the modeling part in the project it has been produced a huge effort to understand how the pressurized chemical looping process would actually work. The Instituto de Carboquimica had already done leading studies on the effect of pressure on kinetics of chemical looping processes mainly working with syngas, see [12, 13]. In this case we decided to apply the methodology previously developed to new oxygen carriers and using biofuels.
2. Main innovation outputs (if applicable)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - new kinetics constants have been developed - new 0D model has been developed and adapted to work in pressurized conditions - new CFD model has been developed in two software: MFiX and Barracuda. This was done in collaboration with a Chinese PhD who was followed and coordinate by the Marie Curie Individual Fellow. The

⁹ https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC2bKUmm7iXO03yYGsUf_oIQ

	software MFIX was used also based on many training sessions performed online during the 2 conferences:
3. Contribution to the state of the art	<p>The contribution to the state of the art of the particle modeling section of workpackage 3 is related with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determination of reaction kinetics at pressurized conditions for a promising Ni-based oxygen carrier to be used in PCLC. Thus, it was determined: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The effect of the CH₄ concentration, C_g, on the t parameter at 5 and 15 atm. T = 779 K. ○ The variation of the reaction rate and the apparent kinetic constant with the total pressure. T = 779 K. ○ The effect of total pressure in the apparent kinetic constant, k_r. T = 779 K. ○ The effect of the reacting temperature on the kinetic constant. • The contribution of the 0D model to the state of the art includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Determination of the fluidization regime in a flow map for the fuel reactor burning CH₄ with ilmenite particles. ○ Relation between design parameters (cross section and solids inventory, m_{FR}) and operating conditions (u_g, ΔP) for the design of the fuel reactor burning CH₄ at different total pressures. ○ Effect of total pressure on the combustion efficiency at several fuel reactor temperatures when the cross section is decreased accordingly to the increase of the pressure drop. ○ Effect of the inlet gas velocity on the combustion efficiency for the bubbling and turbulent regimes. • The Aspen Model and the CFD models contributed to achieve new knowledge on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Process simulation cases. Definitions and model outputs. ○ Energy balance of the CLC cases. Input power = 1 MW_{th} (as CH₄ fed into the FR).
4. Scientific and/or technological quality of the results	<p>The results achieved have high scientific quality. The modeling results have been presented at the Applied Energy Symposium : MIT A+B, 2022 in a keynote speech of 45 by the Marie Curie individual fellow. This has been recorded and it is available in the you tube channel of the project, see¹⁰. The results of the 0D model which analyses chemical looping at pressurized conditions have been published in [4]. The results of the CFD models have been published in [2, 3, 16]. The results of the Aspen Model have been published in [5-8].</p>
5. Comment on secondment(s), if applicable	<p>The secondment at Baker Hughes and the collaboration with Tampere University were useful to calibrate the developed Aspen Model.</p>

¹⁰ https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC2bKUmm7iXO03yYGsUf_oIQ

Table 15: Progress of the activities summary

Type of result	Progress of the activities
1. Main research / innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - activation energy and pre-exponential factor for pressurized chemical looping of nickel based oxygen carrier at different pressures, using biomethane as a fuel. Thus, the activation energy (E_a) was calculated, while the pre-exponential factor, $k_{r,0}$, could be calculated from the y-intercept. The calculated values for these parameters were $k_{r,0}(P=10 \text{ atm})= 204 \text{ m}^{2.28} \cdot \text{mol}^{-0.76} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ and $E_a = 65.8 \text{ kJ/mol}$. - 0D pressurized chemical looping model - CFD models of pressurized chemical looping combustors - ASPEN model of a 12MW gas turbine coupled with a chemical looping combustor
2. Researcher's training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - training on MFIX software during two workshops: NETL 2021 Workshop on Multiphase Flow Science and NETL 2022 Workshop on Multiphase Flow Science - training on ASPEN model on UDEMY - training on ASPEN HYSIS model with colleagues at ICB-CSIC - training on kinetic aspects and thermogravimetric analysis at ICB-CSIC.
3. Transfer of knowledge	<p>Knowledge transfer was relative to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Knowledge of thermogravimetric analysis and kinetics of chemical processes applied to biomass and biofuels - knowledge on reactor modeling in Aspen Plus - knowledge on reactor modeling with 0D models related to biofuels production - knowledge of CFD models applied to multiphase problems.
4. Difficulties or problems encountered; how they were solved (please report any deviations from the Description of the Action -DoA- in section 5)	<p>Computational time was decrease using TRUENO supercomputer with MFIX version running on LINUX system.</p>

WP4: Continuous CLC Reactor tests (April 2022- March 2023)

A Ni-based material patented by CSIC [17] has been used as oxygen carrier for several chemical looping reforming (CLR) process with the purpose of obtaining syngas. Thus, CLR tests were performed previously using CH_4 [18], bioethanol [19] and diesel [20] as fuels.

In this project, the Ni18 α Al oxygen carrier material was selected to be used in CLC tests with the objective of achieving the complete combustion of the fuel. The oxygen carrier was prepared by hot incipient wetness impregnation method [21] using α -Al₂O₃ as support, with a 18wt% of NiO as active phase. Table 1 shows the main properties of the oxygen carrier and the inert support used.

Table 16: Main properties of the oxygen carrier used and the inert support

Sample	α -Al ₂ O ₃	NiO18- α Al ₂ O ₃
Particle size (mm)	0.1–0.3	0.1–0.3
Apparent density (kg/m ³)	2000	2500
Porosity (%)	47.3	42.5
Specific surface area BET (m ² /g)	14.6	7.0
Mechanical strength (N)	–	4.1
XRD phases	α -Al ₂ O ₃	α -Al ₂ O ₃ , NiO, NiAl ₂ O ₄

Bio-oil and glycerol were used as fuel. For the correct feeding of the fuel it was necessary to mix these fuels with distilled water. A H₂O/glycerol molar ratio of 0.25 was used. Also, wood bio-oil with a purity of 68.5 wt% was used. The empirical formula free of water is C₃H₃O, which corresponds to an empirical molecular weight of 55 g/mol. The bio-oil used had one intrinsic H₂O/bio-oil molar ratio of 1.4.

1 kW_{th} CLC UNIT

A 1 kW_{th} Chemical Looping Combustion unit was used for glycerol and bio-oil combustion in the present work, see Fig. 39. The continuous unit is composed of two interconnected fluidized bed reactors (fuel and air reactors), a loop-seal, a riser, a system for gas and liquid feeding and a system for gas analysis. A complete description of the unit can be found elsewhere [19, 20]. In this work, a liquid injector was used to feed glycerol or bio-oil in the fuel reactor, which was located 2 cm above the distributor plate. The injector is composed by three concentric pipes. The fuel is fed in by the inner pipe (o.d. 1/8"). A N₂ flow is injected by a second concentric pipe to increase the velocity in the injection point and therefore to avoid solids return to the pipe. The last pipe is used for water cooling to avoid fuel evaporation before the injection point.

The composition of the gas streams from the fuel and air reactors were determined by several on-line analyzers. In the fuel reactor CH₄, CO, and CO₂ were measured with a non-dispersive infrared analyzer (Siemens/Ultramat 23), and H₂ concentration was determined by using a thermal conductivity analyzer (Maihak S710). In the air reactor, O₂ was measured by a paramagnetic analyzer (Siemens/ Oxymat 5E), and CO₂ by a non-dispersive infrared analyzer (Siemens/Ultramat 23). This latter was used to determine the possible carbon deposition in the fuel reactor that, after being transported to the air reactor, is there burnt.

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Figure 39: 1 kW_{th} CLC continuous unit.

The oxygen carrier inventory in the system was ≈ 2 kg, being ≈ 0.8 kg inside the fuel reactor. The air flow in the air reactor was 1100 NL/h. In the fuel reactor, the total gas inlet flow was 150 NL/h. The glycerol and bio-oil feed flow was 135 and 180 g/h, which means a power input of ca. 650 W_{th}.

In Chemical Looping Combustion the control of the oxygen transferred to the fuel is carried out by controlling the oxygen carrier circulation rate in the unit. The stoichiometric oxygen required for the complete combustion of glycerol and bio-oil to CO₂ and H₂O is 7 and 6.5 mol of NiO per mol of fuel, respectively.

PROCESS EVALUATION

The process performance is evaluated by using the combustion efficiency and the CO₂ capture rate. The combustion efficiency is related to the reactions involving the fuel conversion and the oxygen transference from the oxygen carrier to the fuel. Thus, complete combustion produces CO₂ and H₂O, while CO and H₂ may be produced by a partial oxidation of the fuel. In addition, the fuel may be reformed or decomposed to produce H₂ and CO, or even solid carbon which could be deposited on the oxygen carrier particles, gasified by H₂O or CO₂ and oxidized by NiO. Produced H₂ and CO may also be oxidized by the oxygen carrier. Also, the gas composition may be balanced by the water gas shift reaction or CH₄ could be formed by methanation or as a secondary product of fuel decomposition.

The combustion efficiency, η_{comb} , is calculated considering the unconverted products from the fuel reactor, mainly H₂ and CO, but also CH₄ and accumulated solid carbon on the particles were considered:

$$\eta_{comb} = \frac{sF_f - F_{CO} - F_{H_2} - 4F_{CH_4} - 2F_C}{sF_f} \quad (19)$$

where s is the stoichiometric factor for the complete combustion of the fuel to CO₂ and H₂O, and F_f , F_{CO} , F_{H_2} , F_{CH_4} and F_C are the molar flow of fuel, CO, H₂, CH₄ and accumulated solid carbon on the particles, respectively.

Unconverted solid carbon may be transferred to the air reactor attached to the oxygen carrier particles. In this case, some carbon is burnt by air, and some CO₂ will be found in the exhaust gas stream from the air reactor, which will decrease the CO₂ capture rate (η_{CC}) being calculated as:

$$\eta_{CC} = \frac{cF_f - F_{CO_2,AR}}{cF_f} \quad (20)$$

where c is the number of carbon molecules in the fuel and $F_{CO_2,AR}$ is the molar CO₂ flow from the air reactor.

RESULTS

The combustion tests with glycerin went smooth. Several tests were performed by changing the reactor temperature (750, 800 and 850 °C) and the oxygen carrier circulation rate in order to change the ratio of oxygen in NiO to fuel, $O_{NiO}/fuel$.

Figure 40 shows the gas composition for the different tests with glycerin. The H₂ and CO fractions were decreased as the oxygen to fuel ratio increased. Complete conversion of H₂ and CO to H₂O and CO₂ was not achieved due to the equilibrium condition for the reduction of NiO to Ni. Some CH₄ was also observed which decreased with temperature but it was barely affected by the oxygen to fuel ratio.

Figure 40: Gas composition during CLC tests with glycerin as a function of the $O_{NiO}/Fuel$ ratio and reacting temperature.

As selectivity to CO₂ varied with the operating conditions, different combustion efficiencies were achieved with different oxygen to fuel ratios ($O_{NiO}/Fuel$) and reacting temperatures. Thus, it was required a value of $O_{NiO}/Fuel = 9.5$ to maximize the combustion efficiency. This means that there must be an excess of oxygen with respect to the stoichiometric ($O_{NiO}/Fuel = 7$) of 35 %. To consider the variation of the combustion efficiency with the excess of oxygen, Figure 41 shows its variation as a function of the oxygen carrier to fuel ratio, ϕ , defined by:

$$\phi = \frac{[O_{NiO}/Fuel]_{current}}{[O_{NiO}/Fuel]_{stoichiometric}} \quad (21)$$

Figure 41: Combustion efficiency during CLC tests with glycerin as a function of the oxygen carrier to fuel ratio (ϕ) and reacting temperature.

In addition, no CO_2 was detected in the exhaust gas stream from the air reactor when glycerin was used as fuel. Therefore, the CO_2 capture rate was 100 % in all cases.

The operation with bio-oil was more complex than with glycerin. Under some conditions, the fuel injection system was blocked by carbon deposition. In addition, bio-oil showed a greater trend towards the carbon formation on the oxygen carrier particles. Thus, experimental conditions were limited to 750 and 850 °C, and $\text{O}_{\text{NiO}}/\text{Fuel}$ ratios of 6.5, 8 and 9.5. Considering the stoichiometric $\text{O}_{\text{NiO}}/\text{Fuel}$ ratio for bio-oil is 6.5, the oxygen carrier to fuel ratio, ϕ , was 1.0, 1.2 and 1.5, respectively.

Figure 42(a) shows the fraction of carbon in bio-oil being deposited on the oxygen carrier particles in the fuel reactor. About 20% of carbon was deposited at 850 °C, and it was not affected by the oxygen carrier-to-fuel ratio. In addition, only a small fraction of the deposited carbon was burned in the air reactor. Therefore, the deposited carbon was accumulated on the oxygen carrier particles with the operation time, and the CO_2 capture rate was close to 100% because the presence of CO_2 in the exhaust gas stream from the air reactor was of low relevance; see Figure 42(b). The carbon fraction deposited on the oxygen carrier decreased at 750 °C and it was more reactive than at 850 °C. Thus, about one half of deposited carbon was burned in the air reactor, decreasing the CO_2 capture rate; see Figures 42(a) and 42(b). However, the carbon deposition decreased with the oxygen carrier-to-fuel ratio, and it was undetectable at $\phi=1.5$. Therefore, bio-oil was completely converted to gaseous products in the fuel reactor at 750 °C and $\phi=1.5$.

Figure 42: Effect of the oxygen carrier-to-fuel ratio (ϕ) and the reacting temperature on (a) the carbon fraction being deposited (closed symbols) or accumulated (open symbols) on the oxygen carrier particles; and (b) the CO_2 capture rate.

The gas composition in the fuel reactor is shown in Figure 43 and the combustion efficiency in Figure 44. Unconverted products decreased with the $O_{NiO}/Fuel$ ratio. At 750 °C, the CO/H_2 ratio was about 1, but it increased higher than the unity at 850 °C. In addition, some CH_4 was detected, which also decreased with the $O_{NiO}/Fuel$ ratio. However, most of unconverted product was solid carbon, especially at 850 °C. Thus, the combustion efficiency at 750 °C was higher than at 850 °C. The combustion efficiency at 750 °C and $\phi = 1.5$ was close to the maximum allowed by the equilibrium thermodynamic for the NiO reduction to Ni.

Figure 43: Gas composition during CLC tests with bio-oil as a function of the $O_{NiO}/Fuel$ ratio and reacting temperature.

Figure 44: Combustion efficiency during CLC tests with bio-oil as a function of the oxygen carrier to fuel ratio (Φ) and reacting temperature.

Next, the summary of the results and the progress of the activities is presented in Tables 17 and 18, respectively.

Table 17: Summary of results

Type of result	Description
1. Main scientific and/or technological achievements	<p>- testing a combustion facility with biofuels for the development of bioenergy with carbon capture</p> <p>- proof of concept</p> <p>- use of innovative nickel-based oxygen carriers</p>
2. Main innovation outputs (if applicable)	<p>- proof of concept</p> <p>- high efficiency obtained with the nickel-based oxygen carrier</p> <p>- high purity of CO₂ obtained with the nickel based oxygen carrier</p>
3. Contribution to the state of the art	<p>The contribution to the state of the art is related to the proof of concept of biofuels combustion in a CLC unit. To evaluate the potential of CLC with these fuels, new results on the following aspects have been achieved:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gas composition during CLC tests with glycerin and bio-oil as a function of the O_{NiO}/Fuel ratio and reacting temperature. • Combustion efficiency during CLC tests with glycerin and bio-oil as a function of the oxygen carrier to fuel ratio (ϕ) and reacting temperature. • Effect of the oxygen carrier-to-fuel ratio (ϕ) and the reacting temperature on (a) the carbon fraction being deposited (closed symbols) or accumulated (open symbols) on the oxygen carrier particles; and (b) the CO₂ capture rate.
4. Scientific and/or technological quality of the results	<p>The results obtained in the continuous tests are preliminary results which were needed for the proof of concept. They will be integrated with accurate modeling to understand the effect of high temperatures and pressures and the published as a result of the project.</p>

Table 18: Progress of the activities summary

Type of result	Progress of the activities
1. Main research / innovation	<p>- continuous tests with liquid biofuels;</p> <p>- high combustion efficiency obtained when solid carbon production is limited</p>
2. Researcher's training	<p>- training on continuous chemical looping combustion plants working with liquids</p> <p>- training on loop seal design and working principle</p> <p>- training on liquids injection into a chemical looping combustion plant</p>
3. Transfer of knowledge	<p>The knowledge transferred was on pyrolysis, gasification and combustion of glycerol see the publication of the Marie Curie Individual fellow which was published before the GTCLC-NEG project [22].</p>

4. Difficulties or problems encountered; how they were solved (please report any deviations from the Description of the Action -DoA- in section 5)	Reforming was avoided by adjusting glycerol injection procedure, glycerol and inert gas and water mass flows.
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WP5: Plant design and optimization (April 2022- June 2022)

The procedures and guidelines for pressurized chemical looping combustors design and optimization have been published in [5-8] and developed also during the secondment with Baker Hughes and the collaboration with Tampere University. The steps in the process are the following:

- Firstly, the power capacity of the gas turbine is considered and based on this the air mass flow is calculated, using Aspen Plus and assuming an excess air value which is iteratively optimized trying to reduce fuel consumption and maintaining a Turbine Inlet Temperature constant at 1200 °C;
- Then from the stoichiometric air flow the fuel consumption is calculated (and it is used iteratively to optimize excess air consumption);
- From the optimization process the air reactor and fuel reactor specification are determined, which are used to calculate the mass and energy balances of the air reactor and fuel reactor;
- Then from the box delimited with red dotted lines which is about mass and energy balances optimization we pass to the box delimited with blue dotted lines which is instead on the hydrodynamics optimization we want in fact that both the air reactor and the fuel reactor are close to the fast fluidization regime which allows us to reduce the inventory and so also the operating costs of the plant. This is done by drawing the Grace diagram.

Together with the guidelines the data obtained from the single particle model developed in the Workpackage 3 have been used to define with scientific rigor two main design aspects of a chemical looping combustor:

- the solids inventory, which is defined as the amount of solid which is present at steady state inside the fuel and the air reactor (expressed in kilograms);
- the circulation rate which is defined as the mass flow of oxygen carrier which circulates between the air and the fuel reactor (expressed in kg(s)).

The procedure for these calculations is reported in figures 45 and 46.

DESIGN METHODOLOGY

Figure 45: Guidelines for the design of air reactor and fuel reactor to be coupled to a gas turbine

Figure 46: Procedure for the calculation of the inventory and the circulation rate of the pressurized chemical looping combustor

Finally, the pressurized chemical looping combustor has been optimized based on an energy balance and it has been noted that once the power generated by the gas turbine and its capacity is fixed the efficiency of the entire plant can be maximized by maximizing the excess air which is used to produce that power in the GTCLC-NEG plant configuration, see figure 47.

$$1) \quad Q_{FR} = [(H_{CO_2}^0 * m_{CO_2} + m_{CO_2} * cp_{CO_2} * (T_{FR} - T_0)) + (H_{H_2O}^0 * m_{H_2O} + m_{H_2O} * H_{H_2O}) + (H_{Me}^0 * m_{Me} + m_{Me} * cp_{Me} * (T_{FR} - T_0))] - [(H_{MeO}^0 * m_{MeO} + m_{MeO} * cp_{MeO} * (T_{FR} - T_{AR})) + (H_{CH_4}^0 * m_{CH_4} + m_{CH_4} * cp_{CH_4} * (T_{FR} - T_{comp}))] + VR * \Delta P$$

$$2) \quad Q_{AR} = [H_{MeO}^0 * m_{MeO} + m_{MeO} * cp_{MeO} * (T_{AR} - T_0)] - [(H_{Me}^0 * m_{Me} + m_{Me} * cp_{Me} * (T_{AR} - T_{FR})) + ((m_{O_2st} * (alfa) * cp_{O_2} * (T_{AR} - T_{comp})) + (m_{N_2st} * alfa * cp_{N_2} * (T_{AR} - T_{comp})))] + VR * \Delta P$$

Figure 47: Energy balance inside the pressurized chemical looping combustor

Next, Tables 19 and 20 shows the summary of the results and the progress of the activities, respectively.

Table 19: Summary of results

Type of result	Description
1. Main scientific and/or technological achievements	- development of guidelines for the design of pressured chemical looping combustors to be coupled with a gas turbine. - use of the Aspen Plus model developed in Workpackage 3 and calibration of the model with proprietary software of Baker Hughes company
2. Main innovation outputs (if applicable)	- identification of the optimal configuration of the plant - development of a calculation procedure to optimize the energy balance and the efficiency of the plant
3. Contribution to the state of the art	The contribution to the state of the art is shown in figures: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Guidelines for the design of air reactor and fuel reactor to be coupled to a gas turbine

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Procedure for the calculation of the inventory and the circulation rate of the pressurized chemical looping combustor • Energy balance inside the pressurized chemical looping combustor
4. Scientific and/or technological quality of the results	<p>The results have been published in: [5-8] and revised by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Baker Hughes • University of Tampere • Chalmers University • University of Perugia • University of Zaragoza • SINTEF • Huazhong University of Science and Technology
5. Comment on secondment(s), if applicable	<p>The secondment experience was fundamental to calibrate the Aspen Model with data on the mass and energy balances of a real gas turbine. It was also very useful to understand what is the market of carbon capture technologies to be used for gas turbines and what are the main competing technologies for pressurized chemical looping combustion.</p>

Table 20: Progress of the activities summary

Type of result	Progress of the activities
1. Main research / innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - innovative combustion systems design - carbon negative technologies development in the gas turbine sector
2. Researcher's training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - training on NX2206 Siemens software for gas turbines design - training on IP management procedures in Baker Hughes - Experience as Coal Biomass and Alternative Fuels ASME Committee point of contact - training on gas turbines structure and architecture analysis - training on gas turbines design and operation - training on cybersecurity and data property - training on Allam cycle
3. Transfer of knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - experience in gas turbines modeling and combustion chamber design with CFD software - experience on chemical looping combustion gained in the previous months of the GTLC-NEG project - experience matured in 20 years of participation of the ASME Turbo Expo conference

4. Difficulties or problems encountered; how they were solved (please report any deviations from the Description of the Action -DoA- in section 5)	The maximization of the efficiency of the plant has to be carefully coupled with economic analysis. It is difficult in this case to project many costs of the raw materials and also of the final plant. This was done in collaboration with the company Baker Hughes which assisted on this side.
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Details on the (non-scientific) management activities of the project

Involvement of the researcher in all the management aspects of the fellowship?

The researcher collaborated with the supervisor in the management of the project for what concerns:

- Laboratory safety procedures and safe use of chemicals.
- Team building and leadership experience was constructed through the collaboration with my colleagues: Dr. Arturo Cabello and Dr. Margarita de Las Obras Loscertales
- Results dissemination. As a researcher I contributed to the analysis of our research group scientific production and dissemination activities. I contributed to the dissemination of project results participating to many conferences and sharing links and news with Dr. Francisco Garcia Labiano, who was coordinating dissemination activities in my group. I shared posts of Instagram and links with Isabel Lopez Sarda who was responsible of the public relationship office inside Instituto de Carboquimica. The researcher also participated in the development of graphical supports, like a poster and an open source project dissemination paper which was published by the journal “decarbonization technology” and was used in communication activities.
- Participated to gender balance initiatives of the Spanish National Council of Research (CSIC)
- Coordination with other research groups
- Also communication and dissemination activities were organized in first person by the researcher
- Collaboration with Instituto de Carboquimica Library service for publications registration and upload in the CSIC repository
- Participation to training activities organized by ICB-CSIC and CSIC in general.

Project financial management and support from the administrative staff at the host institution

Project financial management was undertaken by the Researcher together with the supervisor following the internal procedures of the Instituto de Carboquimica. For each mission done outside Instituto de Carboquimica two modules have been filled: Anexo 14a and Anexo 14b. For each acquisition, the following procedure was done:

- Request the offers from the suppliers;
- Selection of the suppliers
- Insert the request for expense in ICB-CSIC website;
- Ask for approval of the supervisor;
- Verification of the purchased goods
- Payment by Gracia Ruiz, Ana Cristina of the secretary office.

The researcher participated actively to the financial management of the action collaborating with Fajes Aznar, Concepción to check salary aspects and taxes. Gracia Ruiz, Ana Cristina for the payment of conferences and Soriano Roche, M^a José for mobility allowance expenses. Besides this I collaborated with my supervisor Dr. Alberto Abad for lab and daily materials expenses. Further training has been done in Coursera with the courses o the iMBA degree on Financial and Project Management Aspect. A course on Project Management which is

propaedeutically for the certification of the Project Management Institute has also been done during the Marie Curie Project.

Another important aspect on the support received by the Instituto de Carboquimica is all the support received during the preparation of the documents which were required to sign the Marie Curie contract. In that case support was provided by the supervisor and by the secretary office in order to:

- Receive a Foreigner Identity Number (NIE), which is assigned by the Police
- The Health Insurance Number release
- The equivalence of the PhD degree
- The management of the personal vehicle registration in Spain and personal vehicle insurance
- Management of the accommodation and other necessities

Integration of the researcher within the host/department

The researcher has been fully integrated in the hosting institution. His name was clearly visible on the Instituto de Carboquimica website. He participated to all the social activities of the Institute (eg. marathon for science, social lunches and dinners etc.). He participated in the periodic group meetings to share the research progress.

Supervision of Master/PhD students

During the Marie Curie Project GTCLC-NEG the Individual Fellow was responsible for the coordination of the activities of a PhD student coming from Huazhong University of Science and Technology to perform PTGA tests and batch reactor tests.

Were there weekly meetings with the supervisor

On each Monday at 10 am a meeting with the supervisor Dr. Alberto Abad was organized either in person or online. Some of the notes taken during these meetings have been scanned and/or written in a digital way and are available in the download section of the website of the project as examples and useful information to understand the work done. Monthly meeting of the research group were organized by the head of the group prof. Juan Adanez. During these meetings the researcher had the possibility to update the group on the progress of the project and of the experimental activities.

Organization of external collaboration, and in the publication of the results?

The researcher during the project was involved to manage the following collaborations:

- Collaboration with Chalmers University, Sweden
- Collaboration with Huazhong University of Science and Technology (HUST), China
- Collaboration with the University of Perugia
- Collaboration with the Coal Biomass and Alternative Fuels Committee of the American Society of Mechanical Engineers (ASME) Turbo Expo, US
- Collaboration with the European Climate Pact Ambassadors Network in Italy and Spain
- Collaboration with the Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA)
- Collaboration with the University of Zaragoza, Spain
- Collaboration with the University of Pisa, Italy
- Collaboration with University of Manchester, UK

Dealing with the publication of results, the GTCLC-NEG publications will be later described (see table 24). In most of the publications realized the researcher has been either corresponding author or first author or both. All the publications contain a reference to the GTCLC-NEG Marie Curie Project.

1.3 Impact

Impact on the researcher's career

The Marie Curie Project was oriented in finding the opportunities and refining the methods to apply for a permanent position as a researcher in most important EU Research Institutes or an assistant/associate/full professor in main EU Universities. Table 21 shows a summary of the applications to Universities or Research Institutes.

Table 21: Results of applications in Universities and Research Institutes Following the experience of the Marie Curie Project

Research Center or University	Position	Achievement
SINTEF	Research Scientist within reactor and process technology	Second out of more than 40 applicants
LIST	E-2366 EXPERIENCED SUSTAINABILITY / LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT ANALYST	Passed the 3 rd and final colloquium
BOKU	Laufbahnstelle (tenure-track) im Fachgebiet Energieverfahrenstechnik mit Schwerpunkt thermochemische Brennstoffumwandlungsverfahren	Presentation and last colloquium in Vienna. Arrived among the first 4 applications.
WURZBURG	W2, Professur für Circular Economy and Life Cycle Assessment (W2)	Invited for Presentation in Wurzburg
GRONINGEN	Tenure Track Assistant Professor Food-Energy-Water Nexus (1.0 Fte)	Invited for presentation and offered a position
ASTON	Lecturer/ Senior Lecturer/ Reader in Chemical Engineering	Invited for last colloquium
LAPPERAANTA	Professorship in Industrial Energy Systems (tenure track)	Selected among the first 4 candidates
STUTGART	W3, Thermische Energie- und Stoffwandlung	Invited for oral presentation
AALBORG	Assistant Professor in Electro fuel/Power-to-X Processes	2 nd and last colloquium
Queens University Belfast	Lecturer/Senior Lecturer/Reader in Engineering, Environment & Sustainability	Invited for interview
University of Perugia	Tenure Track for associate professor position in energy systems	2 nd out of 4 applicants

If we compare the performance of the researcher respect to the past applications which were done before the Marie Curie Project, we can say that the Marie Curie Individual Fellow had already participated in the selection for:

- Associate professor of Circular Economy in Tampere university, arriving 3rd among 4 participants, where 2 were hired;
- Senior Lecturer in Aston University, right before beginning the Marie Curie project and so not accepting the position.
- Arrived among the first applicants for a position of associate professor of Thermal Processes in Lappeenranta University.

Now thanks to the Marie Curie project the invitation for lectures has been definitely increase as it can be seen from table 21. This is also thanks to the work done by partnering with a mental coach who was responsible to train the researcher for the new applications. Besides this the researcher had the possibility to participate to a competition in Italy (in his university of origin) for a tenure track position as associate professor in the field of energy systems (field in which he is habilitated as associate professor already by the Italian National Agency for Evaluation of Research and University System).

The next steps in the career of the researcher will be:

- the researcher has been already object of an invitation letter to a tenure track position for associate professor at the Department of Engineering of the University of Perugia and he is waiting for the final approval of the invitation by the Academic Senate which will gather on the 25th July;
- the researcher on the short term is continuing collaborating with Baker Hughes on two contracts: “evaluation of LCA of the Allam Cycle” and also “Gas turbines components single impact assessment and uncertainty”.
- The researcher has developed and designed a new laboratory to continue the Marie Curie project work and develop BECCS further. For this sake he has already drafted all the required costs for the startup and he has already involved other colleagues like Prof. Vincenzo Spallina and Dr. Alberto Abad in the design of a possible pressurized reactor system, together with the 3D printing lab inside Baker Hughes industrial facility.
- The researcher will graduate at University of Illinois Urbana Champaign in may 2024 receiving an MBA after 3 years of studies which have begun during the Marie Curie project and were self-funded investing the salary of the project itself.
- The researcher will certify his German language knowledge at level B2 which is required by German Universities in 2024;
- The researcher will certify his project management skills with a certification of the Project Management Institute (PMI) at the end of 2023;
- The researcher will increase his consultancy activities in the field of energy and in contemporary increase applications for associate or full professor in Germany.

Innovation capacity, new market opportunities creation, enhancement of competitiveness and growth of gas turbine companies, proposal of solution for issues related to climate change or the environment, addressing industrial and/or societal needs at regional level or bringing other important benefits for society

The work done offers the possibility to gas turbines producing companies to differentiate their business and develop bioenergy with carbon capture and storage technologies (BECCS) which will have a significant market in the future also according to IPCC future energy scenarios.

The GTCLC-NEG concept has been presented in June 2023 in the ASME Turbo Expo Conference and has encountered significant interest from the gas turbine industry. This concept can reduce carbon dioxide concentration from the atmosphere and lead to a decrease of the carbon credit price for companies in future scenarios, as reported by a study performed by the Imperial College and the MIT, see [23].

An approach to the industry has been made during the secondment in Baker-Hughes. New market opportunities have been identified for the Gas Turbine suppliers by integrating chemical looping processes to the energy generation processes.

Information on the relevant innovation activities carried out (eg. prototypes) and/or new products, services, reference materials, processes or methods (to be) launched to the market.

The innovation aspects of the project are multiple, as reported in table 22.

Table 22: Innovation aspects per workpackage

Workpackage	Innovation aspect
Workpackage 1	<p>Main innovation regards the science of materials. It is important to produce properly the synthetic oxygen carriers to understand for example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the interaction between the support (alumina) and the metal oxide which is loaded on the support. This becomes a key aspect when nickel based oxygen carriers are produced. - the structure of the material (both for synthetic and natural oxygen carriers) and its composition in terms of main and trace components. - oxygen vacancies and lattice oxygen migration processes.
Workpackage 2	<p>During the experiments conducted in this workpackage it was found a particular range of conditions of temperature in which the reforming action during the combustion process was reduced and the combustion efficiency was greater. This range was for temperatures comprised between 1100°C and 1200°C.</p>
Workpackage 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - activation energy and pre-exponential factor for pressurized chemical looping of nickel based oxygen carrier at different pressures, using biomethane as a fuel. Thus, the activation energy (E_a) was calculated from the slope of Figure 36, while the pre-exponential factor, $k_{r,0}$, could be calculated from the y-intercept. The calculated values for these parameters were $k_{r,0}(P=10 \text{ atm})= 204 \text{ m}^{2.28} \text{ mol}^{-0.76} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $E_a = 65.8 \text{ kJ/mol}$. - 0D pressurized chemical looping model - CFD models of pressurized chemical looping combustors - ASPEN model of a 12MW gas turbine coupled with a chemical looping combustor
Workpackage 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - continuous tests with liquid biofuels; - high combustion efficiency obtained when solid carbon production is limited
Workpackage 5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - innovative combustion systems design - carbon negative technologies development in the gas turbine sector, for microturbine technology

In table 23 we show the possible exploitable results and the relative exploitation strategy.

Table 23: Exploitable results summary

Results	Possible exploitation strategy
Possibility to realize a prototype of CLC combustor coupled with a micro-gas turbine	Contacts have been taken with Baker Hughes and Canmet Energy. Canmet has developed a pressurized chemical looping concept named the Plug Flow Internally-Circulated Reactor (PFIR) [24], which has a thermal power of 600 kWth and can be successfully coupled to a micro-gas turbine. The process developed in the GTCLC-NEG project can be usefully used for power generation with negative carbon dioxide emissions.
Optimization of temperature management to reduce reforming and optimize combustion efficiency	During the experiments conducted in this workpackage it was found a particular range of conditions of temperature in which the reforming action during the combustion process was reduced and the combustion efficiency was greater. This range was for temperatures comprised between 1100°C and 1200°C. These are also two main exploitable results of the project: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. We have demonstrated that nickel-derived oxygen carriers can be used for pressurized chemical looping combustion at high temperatures; 2. We have identified the optimal duration of the reaction and the optimal temperatures.
Optimization of injection of liquids in CLC plants	The methodology of the continuous tests and the results are the first of this kind. The oxygen carrier inventory in the system was ≈ 2 kg, being ≈ 0.8 kg inside the fuel reactor. The air flow in the air reactor was 1100 NL/h. In the fuel reactor, the total gas inlet flow was 150 NL/h. The glycerol and bio-oil feed flow was 135 and 180 g/h, which means a power input of ca. 650 W _{th} . In Chemical Looping Combustion the control of the oxygen transferred to the fuel is carried out by controlling the oxygen carrier circulation rate in the unit. The stoichiometric oxygen required for the complete combustion of glycerol and bio-oil to CO ₂ and H ₂ O is 7 and 6.5 mol of NiO per mol of fuel, respectively.
Detailed analysis of the oxygen carrier material behavior	Detailed analysis procedure with TGA coupled with kinetics and also materials modeling through Materials Studio software of Biovia has been developed in this project.

Guidelines in developing PCLC plants to be coupled with a gas turbine	Guidelines for the pressurized chemical looping combustor design have been developed in collaboration with Baker Hughes company.
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Contribution towards European policy objectives and strategies and/or impact on policy making

The Power Sector is undergoing a rapid technological change. It is likely that the conventional gas turbines will need to be integrated in systems employing biofuels and/or CCUS (Carbon Capture Usage and Storage), at competitive costs. The EU is moving rapidly towards low carbon technologies (i.e. Energy Efficiency, Smart Grids, Renewables and CCUS), see the Energy Union Strategy. My project addresses two of the four key priorities of the European Energy Union Strategy: i) renewable energy and ii) CCUS, and couples these using breakthrough technologies, such as Chemical Looping Combustion. **If bioenergy is used coupled to CCUS this is called BECCS, which according to the IPCC report of 2014 is a Negative Emission Technology (NET).** To develop Carbon Sequestration Methods was identified by the National Academy of Engineering (NAE) of the United States as one of the Grand Challenges for Engineering. This is a technology of paramount importance for SDG7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) and SDG5 (Climate Action). One of the most effective ways to couple biomass energy and CCUS is to burn biomass or biofuels (i.e. pyrolysis oils, biogas and solid biomass) in a Chemical Looping Combustor, where CO₂ can be easily captured after exiting the fuel reactor.

Potential users of the project results.

Several potential users of the technology developed in the GTCLC-NEG project have been identified, including:

- Baker Hughes (gas turbines producer and oil & gas company),
- General Electrics (gas turbines producer)
- Siemens (gas turbine producer)
- Solar Turbines (gas turbines producer)
- Mitsubishi (gas turbines producer)
- Capstone (microgas turbines producer)
- Ansaldo (microgas turbines producer)
- Valmet (producer of fluidized beds)
- Andritz (producer of fluidized beds)

The gas turbines market is in continuous growth. In 2020 it accounted for \$13.41 billions of dollars and it will grow to 13.80 B in 2021 and 17.29 B in 2028, according to Forbes Business Insights¹¹. Together with Ansaldo and Capstone other micro-gas-turbines producers are: Bladon Micro Turbine (from UK), FlexEnergy Solutions (US), Brayton Energy, LLC (US), Toyota Motor Corporation (Japan), Micro Turbine Technology B.V. (MTT, Netherlands), ICR Turbine Engine Corporation (ICRTec, US), Calnetix Technologies, LLC (US)¹².

Communication with interested industrial sectors has been performed at conferences:

- ASME Turbo Expo, Boston, June 2023, when also a paper on the GTCLC-NEG project has been presented.

¹¹ <https://www.fortunebusinessinsights.com/gas-turbine-market-106255>

¹² <https://www.imarcgroup.com/microturbine-manufacturing-companies>

- 6th International Conference on Chemical Looping 2022 - CLC 2022 – in Zaragoza, Spain. This conference was organised by the Instituto de Carboquímica (ICB-CSIC), hosting institution of the Marie Curie project GTCLC-NEG. It was possible for the researcher to contact in person Dr. Robin Hughes Group Leader, Fluidized Bed Conversion & Gasification, Research Scientist at Canmet ENERGY who signaled interest for the possibility of coupling a micro-gas turbine to a pressurized chemical looping combustion plant. Also in the previously mentioned conference it was possible to see presented works of the University of Manchester, which is working with pressurized chemical looping packed bed reactors.

2. Update of the plan for exploitation and dissemination of results

The plan for exploitation and dissemination of results as described in the DoA does not need to be updated. The list of conferences attended is presented below.

List of the conferences attended

Table 24: List of conferences attended

Conference	Date
Italian Thermotechnical Association Conference 2020	15-16 September 2020, Rome, Italy (online)
NETL 2021 Workshop on Multiphase Flow Science	3-5 August, 2021, online
Advances in Sustainable Research for Energy and Environmental Management (ASREEM-2021)	6-8 August, 2021, Surat, India, (online)
Applied Energy Symposium : MIT A+B, 2021	11-13 August, 2021 (online)
Italian Thermotechnical Association Conference 2021	15-17 September 2021, Rome, Italy (online)
International Conference on Future Prospects of Biological Sciences and Biotechnology	September 23,24 2021, Coimbatore, India (online)
18th Multiphase Flow Conference & Short Course, Dresden 2021	8-12 November 2021, Dresden, Germany (online)
13 th International Conference on Applied Energy, ICAE 2021	November 29 - December 2, 2021, Bangkok, Thailand (online)
4th International Conference on Futuristic Trends in Networks and Computing Technologies (FTNCT-2021)	December 10-11, 2021 Nirma University, India (online)
International Conference on Water, Energy and Environment (WEECON 2021)	December 23 and 24, 2021, (online)
Pre-event of the 3 rd Symposium on Biomass/Wastes Energy and Environment (BEE 2022), Tianjin, China (online)	22nd April 2022
ASME Turbo EXPO 2022	June 13-17, 2022, Rotterdam, Netherlands
NETL 2022 Workshop on Multiphase Flow Science	2-3 August, 2022, online
Applied Energy Symposium : MIT A+B, 2022	5-8, August 2022, online
14 th International Conference on Applied Energy, ICAE 2022	11-8, August 2022, online
Italian Thermotechnical Association Conference 2022	12-14 September 2022, Bari, Italy (in presence)
6 th International Conference on Chemical Looping 2022	19-22 September 2022, Zaragoza, Spain (in presence)

ASME Turbo Expo 2023	26-30 June 2023, Boston, US
6th International Conference on Alternative Fuels, Energy & Environment: Future and Challenges (ICAFEE 2023)	6-8 October 2023, Kayseri, Turkey (in presence).

In the year 2023, the Individual Fellow served as a contact point of the annual 2023 meeting of the Coal, Biomass and Alternative Fuels Committee (CBAF) of the ASME Turbo Expo conference. With the committee, I helped organizing more than 8 sessions, 1 panel sessions and 3 tutorials.

Details on the protection of the acquired intellectual property (patents applications, etc.), if applicable.

The protection of intellectual property has been applied to main results according to ICB-CISC procedures and Baker Hughes procedures. It was possible to publish open source the great part of the results due to CSIC agreement with Elsevier journals. At the moment no patent application is pending on the results of the project. It was also disposed that if patents application will be generated in the future they will be exploited in Europe.

Project dissemination in scientific publications

The published works on the GTCLC-NEG project are listed in table 25 they all contain reference to the EU funds.

Table 25: List of project publications

Number	Publication	Reference	Date
1	Bartocci, P., Abad, A., Cabello, A., de Las Obras Loscertales, M., Zampilli, M., Taiana, A., Serra, A., Fantozzi, F., Development of a Chemical Looping Combustor fed with natural gas and its integration with a gas turbine in ASPEN Plus, Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo 2023: Power for Land, Sea and Air, June 26-30, 2023, Boston, MA USA	[25]	2023
2	Cabello, A., Abad, A., De las Obras Loscertales, M., Bartocci, P., García-Labiano, F., & de Diego, L. F. (2023). Exploring design options for pressurized chemical looping combustion of natural gas. Fuel , 342, 126983.	[4]	2023
3	Lu, W., Bartocci, P., Abad, A., Bisch, A., Yang, H., Cabello, A., ... & Fantozzi, F. (2023). Dimensioning Air Reactor and Fuel Reactor of a Pressurized CLC Plant to Be Coupled to a Gas Turbine: Part 2, the Fuel Reactor. Energies , 16(9), 3850.	[5]	2023
4	Bartocci, P., Abad, A., Bisch, A., Wang, L., Cabello, A., de Las Obras Loscertales, M., ... & Fantozzi, F. (2023). Dimensioning Air Reactor and Fuel Reactor of a Pressurized Chemical Looping Combustor to Be Coupled to a Gas Turbine: Part 1, the Air Reactor. Energies , 16(5), 2102.	[6]	2023

5	Bartocci, P., Abad, A., Flores, A. C., & de las Obras Loscertales, M. (2023). Ilmenite: A promising oxygen carrier for the scale-up of chemical looping. Fuel , 337, 126644.	[1]	2023
6	Lu, W., Bartocci, P., Abad, A., Cabello, A., Loscertales, M. D. L. O., Mendiara, T., ... & Fantozzi, F. (2023). Evaluation of the effect of pressure and heat transfer on the efficiency of a batch fuel reactor, using Iron-based Oxygen Carrier with a CFD model. Fuel , 333, 126266.	[2]	2023
7	Bartocci, P., Bidini, G., Abad, A., Bischi, A., Cabello, A., Loscertales, M. D. L. O., ... & Fantozzi, F. (2022, December). Pressurised Chemical Looping Combustion (PCLC): Air Reactor design. In <i>Journal of Physics: Conference Series</i> (Vol. 2385, No. 1, p. 012127). IOP Publishing.	[7]	2022
8	Bartocci, P., Abad, A., Mattisson, T., Cabello, A., de las Obras Loscertales, M., Negredo, T. M., ... & Fantozzi, F. (2022). Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS) developed by coupling a Pressurised Chemical Looping combustor with a turbo expander: How to optimize plant efficiency. Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews , 169, 112851.	[8]	2022
9	Bartocci, P., Abad, A., Bischi, A., Wang, L., Cabello, A., de Las Obras Loscertales, M., ... & Fantozzi, F. (2023). Design of the air reactor for a Chemical Looping Combustion plant coupled with a turbo expander, 14th International Conference on Applied Energy - ICAE2022, Aug. 8-11, 2022, Bochum, Germany.	[26]	2022
10	Bartocci, P., Abad, A., Cabello, A., de las Obras Loscertales, M., Lu, W., Yang, H., & Fantozzi, F. (2022). CFD Modelling of the Fuel Reactor of a Chemical Loping Combustion Plant to Be Used with Biomethane. Processes , 10(3), 588.	[3]	2022
11	Bartocci, P., Abad, A., 2022. Realisation of a carbon negative combustor for gas turbines, <i>Decarbonization Technology</i>	[27]	2022
12	Bartocci, P., Abad Secades, A., Obras-Loscertales, M. D. L., Cabello Flores, A., Taiana, A., Joronen, T., ... & Fantozzi, F. (2021). Batch fluidized bed model in MFIX software for simulation of chemical looping combustion. (Poster)	[28]	2021
13	Bartocci, P., Abad, A., Cabello, A., Zampilli, M., Buia, G., Serra, A., ... & Fantozzi, F. (2021). Technical economic and environmental analysis of chemical looping versus oxyfuel combustion for NGCC power plant. In <i>E3S Web of Conferences</i> (Vol. 312, p. 08019). EDP Sciences.	[29]	2021
14	Bartocci, P., Abad, A., Cabello, A., de las Obras Loscertales, M., Pelucchi, M., Taiana, A., Lu, W., Yang, H., Zhao, H., Yang, Q., 2021, Technical economic and environmental analysis of chemical looping versus oxyfuel combustion for NGCC power plant, <i>E3S Web of Conferences</i> , EDP Sciences, 312	[16]	2021

List all the outreach activities undertaken (visit to schools, Researchers' Night, etc.).

The list of the outreach activities is proposed in table 26.

Table 26: List of outreach activities

Outreach activities	Date and Place
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EU Researchers Night 21	24 th September 2021, Caixa Forum, Zaragoza, Spain (in person)
Science is Wonderful 21	22-26 November 2021, online
EU Researchers Night 2022	30 th September 2022, Caixa Forum, Zaragoza, Spain (in person)
Sumo Science 23	1 st February 2023, online
Sumo Science 23	18 th April 2023, online
Workshop at Aston University, Birmingham, UK	May 2023, Birmingham, UK

Social media, press-release, the project web site, video/film

In the figures 48-50 the twitter website, the GTCLC-NEG project website and the you tube channel of the project are presented. They all include a reference to EU funding.

Figure 48: Twitter website of the GTCLC-NEG project

Figure 49: GTCLC-NEG project website

Figure 50: You tube channel of the project GTCLC-NEG

3. Update of the Data Management Plan (if applicable)

The data management plan has not changed and remains as it was described in Deliverable D2.1. In most of cases, data will be available on demand.

4. Deviations from Annex 1 and Annex 2 (if applicable)

- no deviations from the DoA, have happened.

4.1 Tasks

All the tasks have been fully implemented.

4.2 Use of resources

Not applicable for MSCA-Individual Fellowships.

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[This is the end of the technical report part B.]